

Reputation Final Report

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Executive summary

This deliverable reports on the experiences and the voices of women who have played vital inspirational roles and shared success stories, contributing to shape the shemakes ecosystem. They have emerged as drivers and mobilisers of change.

They tell their stories and narratives, highlighting their approach to innovation from their own perspectives. Advisors speak with the voice of experience, while the Gurus actively built the ecosystem in collaboration with the Transfer Labs, activating a transfer of knowledge across the entire ecosystem of shemakes and future lab spaces. Finally, the Ambassadors bring in new stories based on their experiences in shemakes activities, bringing a sense of flourishing and sharing to the young generation of innovators. Ultimately, this document illustrates the individual perspectives and their different roles in promoting innovation.

Chapter one reflects on the iterative process and the implementation of WP4 in collaboration with the other work packages.

Chapter two reviews the Advisory Board's feedback with their insights on how to steer shemakes actions, shared through their voices and Interviews. Notably, the Advisory Board provided important input for the expansion strategy of the shemakes ecosystem for the second phase of the project. In addition, they emphasised the connection to the reality of the textiles and clothing industry by expressing a sense of urgency for sustainable alternatives, the drive towards new methodologies, and the respect and admiration for the ongoing work and innovation generated by the Lab's activities.

Chapter three discusses the role of the Gurus and the support activities carried out in the second phase, specifically addressed to the Transfer Lab leaders and the Ambassadors. It is important to note that the Gurus provided the link between phase one and the coordination and alignment of all activities and methods applied with the Transfer Labs in phase two. For this, they received the first impulse from the WP leaders, particularly WP2 and WP3, and were thus able to learn and iteratively apply the knowledge and methods developed to advise the Transfer Labs, support the design of the new activities, and promote exchange within the shemakes community. This included providing guidance to the Ambassadors on their role in the assigned Transfer Lab. The Gurus thus played a pivotal role in building the shemakes ecosystem, developing strong collaborative links with the Transfer Labs and with each other.

Chapter four introduces the Ambassadors and their role in the knowledge exchange with the Transfer Labs. Different meetings, tools and methodologies were presented to

build a process and line of action for building an expanded innovation ecosystem. These tools and methods were co-created with all partners with the input of the Gurus themselves, linking the work of WPs 2 and 3 to create working methods and good practice towards the goal of innovation and collaboration as documented in the open toolkit.

Section 4.3 illustrates the first ambassadors' stories through their experiences in their roles, following the steps of: arrival, first contact with the assigned Transfer Lab, development of the activities, and reflections on their experience. This feedback demonstrates the great potential of taking action and promoting knowledge transfer while confronting the new realities of the Transfer Labs.

Section 4.4 introduces the second round of Ambassadors, selected in the final months of the project, with the goal of expanding the shemakes ecosystem and broadening participation to males, to prepare and support the Ambassadors for opening up opportunities for future interactions.

Chapter four closes with the impact of the final shemakes conference, organised jointly with the TCBL network, gathering testimonies from different innovators in "Welcoming Differences". The conference highlighted the opportunities for visibility and sharing meaningful narratives in their roles while engaging in the shemakes ecosystem.

Chapter five presents the windows of visibility accompanied by the communication team and complemented by the presence of the role models in the media.

This deliverable concludes with the findings and reflections on the experience of reputation management overall five aspects: the role of the human factor, the dimensions of collaboration, implications for the future of the shemakes labs, building a caring ecosystem and the methodologies and tools provided by this journey. It also suggests future steps for the expansion of the system of role models in future initiatives, highlighting two important actions. The first is the documentation and open access of the WP4 material in the open toolkit to make it available for future Advisors, Gurus and Ambassadors. The second is the suggestion, based on our two years of experience, to re-conceptualised this WP with the name "Role Models and Innovation Narratives", to better reflect the content and resources that can be found by building a community and innovation ecosystem through collaboration.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Description of the deliverable

D4.3 Reputation: Final Report (lead partner: MATR; PU; M24) is a summative report on the reputation management activities, including the role of the Advisors and their contributions to the project, the results of Guru mentoring both locally and for network expansion, and the identification of the final set of 18 Ambassadors including the three selected as testimonials for the shemakes Final Conference.

1.2. Context and Objectives

The shemakes project is dedicated to the mission, experience, value and growth of women's roles in innovation through inspiration, skills and networks. In this context, WP4 highlights the human factor¹ and the interaction from the individual experience to the collective contribution of the shemakes community. These elements can be seen in the three roles of Advisors, Gurus and Ambassadors, which represent: 1) in opening minds through inspiration and advice to achieve the goals; 2) building an ecosystem in which everyone understands the opportunities and barriers, enabling its actors to establish mutual confidence to contribute to its development; 3) in building and sharing collective competencies such as group management knowledge and lab skills, with the ultimate goal of leading and inspiring local communities while sharing stories and reflections globally.

In this way, shemakes role model networks understand and create a sense of belonging, creating opportunities to grow collectively as a living innovation ecosystem. During the project, Reputation management promoted the collaborative building of a community through three types of leading figures, each with a precise aim.

Advisors

As leading figures in research, innovation and business, with an emphasis on the T&C sector, bring in their vision as they closely follow the shemakes phases. Their interviews inspire the community and resonate with the shemakes values. Notably,

¹ The psychological, cultural, behavioral, and other human attributes that influence decision-making, the flow of information, and the interpretation of information by individuals or groups.

<https://www.definitions.net/definition/Human%20Factors>

their advice has contributed to giving direction and highlighting strengths and weaknesses during the project's expansion phase.

Gurus

As leaders of partner labs, they engage within the project by transforming its strategic vision through its operationalisation in the different Learning Paths and Lab activities, especially by mentoring the 12 Transfer Labs participating in the second phase of activities.

Ambassadors

As the exchangers in the ecosystem, bring the shemakes experience alive and create a peer-to-peer transfer of knowledge, inspiring a new responsive and collaborative vision of role models. In addition, they brought insights to the new labs through the exchange of the Learning Paths and Innovation Services, as transfer agents for expanding the network and testimonials of the shemakes experience.

WP4 also focused on giving **visibility to these role models** by encompassing the actions of all the individual and collective profiles and encouraging the dissemination of stories in the media, exchanging experiences in the group and in on-site meetings, and sharing results of the shemakes efforts.

1.3. Methodology and activities carried out

Following the delivery of D4.1, Reputation Management in the next steps carried out parallel efforts to accompany the three different groups on their respective timelines. In line with the phases described in the DoA, here is an adaptation based on the focus of the reputation management contribution during months 12 to 24.

Reputation building and transition (M10-M12)

Highlight, with the project partners and in particular the Gurus and Ambassadors, the increased value of skills and the prospects for increased equity for women, leading to the transition towards the second iteration of shemakes Lab activities with the enlarged network of 18 Labs. This involved the following actions:

- Advisors' feedback on the first phase activities.
- Gurus' collaborative vision for the future activities of the Transfer Labs .(timeline of actions), and the 'Gift weave challenge' activity.
- Ambassadors' first selection.
- Visibility of Ambassadors.

Innovation actions Phase 2 (M13-M18)

All partners developed a timeline for the second iteration of shemakes Lab activities promoting multi-faceted innovation through the Gurus, Ambassadors and Transfer Lab leaders articulating the content. A summary of actions is as follows:

- Co-organization of the activities.
- Bi-weekly meetings in plenary sessions for Labs, Gurus, and Ambassadors.
- Ambassadors' meetings, accompanied by the use of a sketchbook as a guiding tool.
- One-to-One Sessions (Ambassadors, Gurus, and Transfer Lab leaders).

Reputation building and diffusion (M19-M21)

Collect and identify the Gurus' and Ambassadors' learnings from the previous phase, with the support of the Advisory Board members, to demonstrate the increased value to the broader networks of Fabricademy and TCBL Labs. In particular, this period brought feedback on the impact of the values and the changes in efforts to bring women into the innovation ecosystem, while defining the final iteration of tools for shemakes Lab activities. Here is a recap of the activities:

- Gurus' and Ambassadors' experiences and reflections.
- Ambassadors' 2nd Call and Selection.
- Guru contact and support during these experiences.
- Advisory Board feedback session on the second phase.

Consolidation of results (months M22-M24)

Recap the entire journey of shemakes Lab activities and increase the values and skills to consolidate the contribution of the individual and collective efforts through the different kinds of collaboration. These result in the creation of tools, businesses connections, and the empowerment of Gurus, Ambassadors and Labs leaders as the carriers for the further development of the shemakes innovation ecosystem and the broader uptake of the shemakes approach post-project, with an impact on increased equity for women in society. Here is a recap of the consolidating activities:

- Final Documentation of the activities in the Open Toolkit repository,
- Ambassador 2nd Call activities to prepare shemakes sustainability.
- Final conference with the reflections of the Ambassadors, Gurus, and Advisors.

A summary of these activities can be found in the figure below.

Figure 1. Summary of reputation management activities for Advisors, Gurus & Ambassadors.

2. Advisory Board

2.1. Overview

The Advisory Board is one of the three role models used in the shemakes project to provide inspiration and guidance to the consortium and the community.

After the first year of the project, the Advisory Board continued to work towards three main objectives:

- Provide inspiration for the labs and the participants who joined the shemakes network, thanks to their own experience as innovators and game changers in the textile and clothing sector.
- Give feedback to the consortium partners on the outcomes of WPs 2 and 3 as transferred to the new labs in the community.
- Contribute to reflect on the key learnings and the next steps for the project overall

Targets and Changes

The group of Advisors was slightly revised in 2022, as Valeria Valotto replaced Mara Balestrini after she joined a new company in the US, and Bill Macbeth was added as a male ally to the shemakes community, following recommendations from the first Advisory Board meeting and the project mid-term review.

The current set of Advisors includes:

- **Aurélie Mossé**, co-director of the Soft Matters group at Ensad Lab in Paris (FR).
- **Bill Macbeth** (new in 2022), managing director of the Textile Center of Excellence in Huddersfield (UK).
- **Daniela Toccafondi**, director of Prato Futura in Prato (IT).
- **Gabriela Macoveiu**, director of the Regional Development North-East in Iasi (RO).
- **Grace Jun**, CEO at the Open Style Lab in New York (US).
- **Marte Hentschel**, CEO of the Sqetch platform in Berlin (DE/NL).
- **Rebecca Earley**, co-founder of the Center for Circular Design at UAL in London (UK).
- **Silvia Brandi**, CEO of the Atlas of the Future (ES/AT).
- **Valeria Valotto** (new in 2022), VP at Progetto Quid in Verona (IT).

This group represents a variety of stakeholders, including members of research & academia, training & teaching, business consultancy & support, entrepreneurs & SMEs and policy development, as a means to gain multiple insights into the results of the project. Two Advisors' organisations were also selected as Transfer Labs in Phase 2.

Information collection and interaction

The main methods used to meet the three objectives above were the following:

- Inspiration and input were provided through **online interviews** streamed on the shemakes website and social media. These started in September 2021 and were planned approximately once a month until May 2022. Only for Bill Macbeth, who joined later in the process, the online interview was replaced by a questionnaire and a blog article. Most of them were in English except for two - one in Italian and one in Romanian - that were later subtitled. Inspiration was also given through keynote speeches in a variety of online meetings during the project, such as the gender vision workshops and Wool Mondays.
- In continuation with the **online feedback meeting** that took place after the 1st phase of the shemakes project (November 2021), the Advisors' contribution to the outcomes of the 2nd phase took place in an online meeting that took place in October 2022. Here, the key results of the project were presented and questions about the next steps for the sustainability of the community were raised and discussed. For the three Advisors who were not present, a second catch-up meeting was held in early November.
- Further inspiration and guidance were brought to the community at the **final shemakes conference** in Amsterdam at the end of November 2022, where two Advisors (Rebecca Earley and Bill Macbeth) delivered keynote speeches to outline specific themes, and the majority participated in the online Q&A sessions.

2.2 Main insights from the Advisors

Projects insights on the go

Advisors first provided insights to help the consortium transition from Phase 1 with the 6 initial Core Labs to Phase 2 with the 12 additional Transfer Labs. To focus on themes related to the ongoing project, a common interview canvas of questions was developed and proposed to different partners of the consortium who were conducting the streamlined interviews.

The main questions of this canvas were:

- **Change story and skills:** What was the turning point that woke you up to the need to personally *do something to change* the textile and fashion industry? Did you undergo formal training in your career? How did you gain the *skills* to get to where you are today? Knowing that *creativity* doesn't happen in a vacuum, what external elements or inspirations have contributed to your work?
- **Gender focus:** During your training or in business today, did you encounter any *barriers or challenges*? Did any of these relate to being a *woman*? Is your *gender relevant* to the work you do and the way you do it? Do you think there is a need to *encourage women* to work in your sector? And how might we do that together?
- **Sustainability focus:** Have you observed a *change* in perceptions of sustainable fashion, your work or your sector in recent years? *Why*? What are the innovation and methods that are most likely to *disrupt* the T&C industry and push it *towards greater sustainability*?
- **Advice to future female innovators:** What advice do you have for future women innovators?

The main insights gained for the ongoing projects were:

- **Change story and skills:** the importance of knowledge and training, including core T&C skills, soft skills, and creativity and innovation and the need to constantly update skills.
- **Gender focus:** the need to attract men to fashion to improve the women/men balance at all levels of organisation, while supporting women as decision-makers and leaders; engage with optimism, using labour discrimination as a source of talent.
- **Sustainability focus:** the need for deep change in the industry, looking at socio-environmental needs all along the value chain; biomimetics and bio-design with sustainability as a source of competitive advantage.
- **Advice to female innovators:** suggestion to trust intuition, dare to explore frontiers, and find a clear niche or a blind spot, creating teams with diverse and complementary skills; the need to search for excellence beyond regular standards, tell great stories, network for clients, network for production and contact female-friendly financiers, while nourishing courage and passion.

For each interview, the main insights have been edited and are reported in the table below.

Table 1. Main insights from Advisor Interviews.

Voices	Insights
Aurélie Mossé	<p>Sustainability and gender equality started as popular academic issues in Northern Europe 20 years ago. Sustainable design is about solving new design challenges to respect nature, e.g. weaving a garment from the loom, and thinking about the next sustainability stage, which is about bio-design, designing with the living, e.g. bacteria.</p> <p>In France now, the needs are to attract men as regular textile designers and to make women designers greater leaders, decision-makers or entrepreneurs by teaching them to trust their own intuition, create a supportive team and think beyond boundaries.</p>
Bill Macbeth	<p>In the textile and clothing sector, sustainability has become a competitive advantage.</p> <p>Innovation does happen, when you train everyone in a textile company on hard and soft skills, that support the development of a competitive base of local manufacturing companies (in Yorkshire and the UK.), which in turn can be mobilised to work on future fashion projects.</p> <p>Launching a new business is about knowledge of business, excellence above industry standards, quality and reliable sourcing, niche products, earning money to live, and finding financial support.</p>
Daniela Toccafondi	<p>Academia, connection to the local industry in Prato and a great ability to network were key elements of success for her generation.</p> <p>On top of that, women innovators now need courage and passion, and should master science and mathematics to develop independence of thoughts and of work.</p> <p>To throw themselves in a business world, women should understand the mental models of organisations to be able to deal with them or change them, and/or work in connected groups of SMEs to reinforce their power.</p>
Gabriela Macoveiu	<p>As the European Textile and Clothing industry is the second in producing waste, change is about more than raising the low pay of current female workers: it's about a deep transformation of the industry towards sustainability.</p> <p>T&C sustainable businesses are no longer a utopia as more businesses use textile waste as their main resource or design sustainable products and services.</p> <p>Launching a new business means that women learn how to innovate and develop practical innovation skills. It also requires risk-taking, networking and responsibility for people that will be employed by this new generation of innovators.</p>
Grace Jun	<p>Contribution to change was high in the pandemic and helped move from technology design to inclusive and human-centred design driven by multi-disciplinary teams. More generally, opportunities for women</p>

Voices

Insights

	<p>are embedded in new, unexplored grounds, e.g. crossing intersectionality with disability in fashion design.</p> <p>Being trained to launch a project or a new activity is based on training that, even if available everywhere, benefits from a lab context, as the lab becomes a reference for each target audience and supports women in getting out of their comfort zones to realise their dreams.</p>
Marte Hentschel	<p>Sustainability starts with looking in depth at changing the value chain, taking into account its environmental and social pressures. It is also about the development of hybrid competency profiles, e.g. engineers thinking like designers, managers or leaders and vice versa. Focussing on women's roles, sustainability relies on equality at all levels of the organisation's hierarchy.</p> <p>Advice to help women launch a new business would be to start as a team with complimentary skills, and with a network of supportive people who can mentor and advise.</p>
Rebecca Earley	<p>Sustainable fashion was already part of the innovative and creative London fashion scene 30 years ago. Exploring how to reduce the environmental impact of printing started with making only personalised printed garments with very low amounts of ink and slowly evolved into a circular design approach. One of the future challenges in dyeing could be how to re-print on old prints.</p> <p>For women today who want to venture into changing the T&C sector, some kind of recipe could be: get new ideas, learn and use frameworks to unfold them, have the right core skills to research your prototypes, get your community to help you make final products, switch from artisan to small scale, and learn how to tell great stories to sell your collection or change people's minds.</p>
Silvia Brandi	<p>In the T&C sector, sustainable practices are urgent to pass on, to ensure a better world and protect future generations.</p> <p>Innovation and creativity should be integrated to tackle these challenges. Local action, e.g. in the Austrian renovated sheep farm, is important as well as global knowledge, e.g. Atlas of the future.</p> <p>Positive change is first based on optimistic inspiration to other people, women and men. "Optimism is activism" as it helps reach out to more people, who in return are willing to engage in contributing to more positive change.</p>
Valeria Vallotto	<p>Change towards sustainability starts when you see the potential of transformation of the limits, e.g. end of rolls to become new garments, which is of greater interest to women even if sourcing is cross gender.</p> <p>Ethical fashion is also based on less discrimination in labour markets, e.g. people suffering from previous traumas such as human-trafficking.</p> <p>Training and empowerment sessions are the base to transform these discriminated people into innovators. Measurements of success range</p>

from financial self-sufficiency to satisfaction of B2B clients with the products proposed.

2.3. Insights from the second feedback session

A second feedback session including key project partners and the Advisory Board members was scheduled for the month of October 2022 in order to present the outcomes and results from the second phase of activity and discuss plans for post-project sustainability.

The session in fact unfolded as two sessions due to scheduling issues, the first one was held on September 28th, with Advisors Silvia Brandi, Marte Hentschel, Aurélie Mossé and Bill Macbeth attending, and the second one happened on November 17th, 2022, to further incorporate comments from Gabriela Macovieu and Grace Jun. Advisors were presented the numerous outcomes of Phase 2 in order to get their feedback on what they believed were key results and to debate on how to improve the prospects for the sustainability of the network.

The main feedback from the discussion can be synthesised in the following points:

Communicate project outcomes clearly and synthetically.

- State the challenge addressed, use facts and figures.
- Clarify the barriers and infrastructure issues as they have been encountered.
- Clarify the vision and approach in a way that is easy to understand: what change is/can be expected.
- Present results and impacts, link to KPIs and results against expectations, what has been learned, what changes have been brought about, what has been the impact on attitudes.
- Clarify how impact is measured and assessed.
- Focus on the legacy to stakeholders, what have they gained? Labs, companies, participants...

Develop the methodology also for application in other areas

- The methodology for collaborative and distributed research, tightly linked with the vision, is itself an innovative result: how to build a dedicated ecosystem.
- Highlight the community building approach, continue to engage with communities and offer involvement in lab activities, illustrating the

opportunities of reflecting diversity by building the overall community and having a broader scope of inclusion.

- The reputation management approach shows the central role of collaboration and the different types of role models to develop an ecosystem approach. These methodological issues are also a worldwide concern for wicked problems in general.
- Focus on documentation to allow for diffusion, distribution, follow-up.

Continue the research activities

- Identify the activities that can be replicated in the future.
- Explore the possibility to continue developing the wool project.

Keep the focus on the gender perspective

- Gender equality is both an end goal and a driver of community and innovation. The gender perspective provides a new way of looking at the research issues.
- The gender issue looks at how people have been denied opportunities from the start. The question is how to bring people into the system, how to bring them up to speed.
- Focusing only on the leaders is not enough, as the ripple effect doesn't work. Gender is very much an infrastructure issue, with male domination of education, capital, investment, etc.
- We need to frame the gender issue as one of market failure and lost opportunities for the industry in general. We cannot necessarily change the industry but the role of women can grow. We can demonstrate impact in these terms.
- Maintain the shemakes identity to keep the gender perspective alive and active, implement through concrete actions such as the wool project.

Position the shemakes vision

- Relate the vision for open and collaborative working methods to the existing industrial structures – the old systems are not going to change, we need to be realistic.
- Clearly define sustainability – it means different things to different people.
- Adopt a Now – Near – Far approach to mapping the emergent ecosystem with respect to traditional infrastructures and practices at different points along a time scale.

- Apply a systemic lens to see the potential for change, using tools to develop different scenarios. Then it is possible to define a transition path that can lead us from here to there.
- Generate a chain reaction through social media, focus on Instagram (hand-over of the channel), highlight what women can do in relation to the big challenges of gender / circularity / climate.
- Develop the unconventional career paths discovered in the course of the project – how people end up where they are, often following unusual trajectories and with a rich baggage of experience.

Make specific provisions within TCBL and Fabricademy

- It is important to provide an institutional framework for sustainability.
- Specific relevant spaces – e.g. the new VORN fashion hub in Berlin – can provide visibility for sharing results and expanding the network.
- Merge with the labs network of TCBL, but form a “Shemakes Club” within TCBL for continuity with the project actions, meeting online and in person at regular intervals. Shemakes can be considered as a further development of the social dimension first explored in TCBL.
- Fabricademy is not only about technology, it helps people learn to be creative, to learn and to explore opportunities. Fabricademy also serves as the source of income for future use of the toolkit through different business models currently offered.
- Define the governance model for maintenance and updating of the shemakes toolkit and related resource, based on the Shemakes Club and transversal to both TCBL and Fabricademy.
- Within the approach for sustainability through TCBL and Fabricademy, it is important to provide a clear entry point into the Shemakes Club. Who to contact, where to start. A clear strategy for how to scale, how to engage is needed. It has to be easy to join, easy to support.

Look for funding and related opportunities

- Promote project outcomes within the Commission services, gain visibility within specific initiatives and communities.
- Link to related initiatives e.g., the World Circular Textiles Day, bringing in the gender perspective with projects such as wool.
- Link to regional policies, important strategic opportunities at all levels.
- The academic environment can provide one channel to keep the network alive. Possibility for linked or networked PhD theses, funded publications.

- Follow-up funding opportunities related to inclusion but also to innovation, skills, industry, etc. It is important to bring the gender perspective into related fields of research. In parallel, the shemakes methods and approach can be applied in different contexts. A broad range of Calls for Proposals can be relevant to shemakes follow-up.

3. Gurus

The Gurus - members of the project partners and in most cases directors of the Labs or managers of educational and entrepreneurial activities - have been leaders and mediators in the management of the Transfer Labs and in the transfer of knowledge between the Transfer Labs and the Ambassadors. In addition to activating their local communities, they have done a remarkable job in understanding the context of the Transfer Labs, illustrating and transmitting the shemakes values, grasping and guiding the practical and logistical aspects of the activities, and co-creating a joint reflection and exchange with the Ambassadors for the local and global community. They also promoted the role of the leaders of the Transfer Labs by fostering a space for collaboration and gender equality as community leaders. In addition, they provided valuable support, embodying the charisma of the network of female shemakes role models by appropriating, building and nurturing a sense of belonging to the shemakes community.

As the DoA mentions, the Gurus contribute in the following ways:

- Capture relevant knowledge from on-going research and/or activities within the Fabricademy and TCBL networks and be able to contextualise it in specific lab settings.
- Project knowledge and innovation developed in specific lab communities through the shemakes network.
- Accompany the integration of new labs that are interested in their specific line of activity into the network.

3.1. New gurus for phase two

Following the suggestion of the Advisory Board to include more male participation, contribute and have awareness and perception of the barriers and opportunities in gender differences, **Elvys Sandu** was included as Guru in the second phase. As a member of project partner Mai Bine, Elvys actively participated from the beginning of the project and was an essential source of verification in the vision and collaborative work among women. In addition, Elvys contributed, listened, and gave advice to the shemakes project. Together with Andreea Sofronea forming the REDU lab team, he contributed to diversity in building Task 3.1 Community Engagement.

The second change was **Shannon Sykes**, who led the activities of project partner ONL'FAIT. As Guru, she managed, led and exchanged experiences, especially in the project's second phase. This leadership meant a new challenge for her and, at the

same time, a great learning experience in her professional development for the organisation of the two Transfer Labs and the exchange of the Ambassadors, especially building links with the French-speaking network. Below are their biographies:

- **Elvys Sandu:** *Elvys co-organised one of the first electronic music festivals in Iasi, Electrees, more than 15 years ago; graduated in fashion design with a master in Slow Fashion at the Faculty of Visual Arts and Design in Iasi; replaced his car with a bicycle, even for trips of hundreds of kilometres; collects music and shares it under the stage name The Dreamer and plays the drums for one hour a week. Elvys is currently co-coordinator on European textile research and innovation projects and president at Mai bine, as well as the designer, maker, and co-owner of REDU. Among the goals of the projects he is currently working on are: building and catalysing resilient communities, new circular (bio-based) textiles, circularity guides for future designer-textile makers, transparency and traceability of the textile industry production chain through blockchain and empowering future women innovators in a sustainable fashion.*
The activist spirit is grown and nurtured at Mai bine, where for 7 years he has been helping with many of the association's activities: urban gardening, food collection and redistribution, protests, turning Cuib into a zero-waste bistro, promoting sustainable living in theory and practice, etc.
- **Shannon Sykes:** *Shannon is curious to know and understand the world around us, she has had a big thirst for learning. She trained as a model maker at the Arts University Bournemouth where she learned how to mix traditional to numerical processes and techniques while working with a variety of materials from metal and wood to plastics.*
She is currently working at On'fait's fab lab in Geneva. She is a project manager, modelling referent, 3D printers and digital embroiderer. She also participates and teaches in other projects that touch on Biomaterials, mycelium, kombucha, leather moulding using a parametric program, and bacterial dyeing. This allows her to learn and experiment in different fields. In addition, she had the chance to participate in a course by the Ars Electronica Festival and the fab fest challenge 2022 in Bali, where she experienced collaboration from people all around the world by problem-solving current and local issues.

3.2. Activities supporting the transition from Phase 1 to Phase 2

As described in D4.2, three activities were carried out to support the Guru's role :

- The **Gift Weave Challenge**² was an activity organised during the face-to-face consortium meeting in Barcelona. This activity involved the Guru's contribution to the next phase.
- An **innovation analysis** workshop aimed to create a space to exchange methods of collaboration and understand the methods and innovation that Gurus and Transfer Lab leaders are implementing in their labs. In the following section, we describe the activity's insights and the results.
- Finally, the activity "**From Gurus to Transfer Labs**" encapsulated the different dynamics of the Gurus involved in the second phase and aimed to bring the Gurus and Ambassadors together with the 12 Transfer Labs.

The Innovation Analysis workshops

Deliverable [4.2](#) describes the design of the "Innovation Analysis" workshops planned for the Gurus and Transfer Lab leaders for the second phase of the shemakes project. The activities outlined there took place with the Gurus from the Partner Labs and the Gurus from the Transfer Labs.

In the first part, a broader understanding of innovation was presented, with a further addition to the innovation methodologies in the shemakes innovation ecosystem³. The concept of agility was introduced as a fundamental component in innovation processes, which can be applied to the process of prototyping and production in shemakes labs. Through this activity, it was expected that participants reflect on how the process of innovation is situated in shemakes, in terms of cultural agility (lab values) and technical agility (application of tools and methods). Finally, participants identified elements of cultural agility that could be reflected in the shemakes ecosystem. This approach can be described as the mindset for working agile and is embedded in a team, as shown in figure 2.

² This activity is described in the D4.2 Reputation: Interim Report. Page 30

https://shemakes.eu/sites/default/files/doc/p/files/D4.2_23.12.2021%2023-12-2021%20at%2012.20.06.pdf

³ More information about the innovation methodology and Innovation ecosystem can be found in the D1.1 shemakes vision https://shemakes.eu/sites/default/files/doc/p/files/su_21oct31_d1.1.pdf

Figure 2. Levels of agility.⁴

A total of 18 labs, including Partner and Transfer Labs, were invited to participate in two separate workshop sessions. The workshop with Partner Labs was held on February 23, 2022, and the Transfer Labs session was held on April 28, 2022. Of the 18 labs invited, 14 participated in the workshops. The innovation analysis was divided into four areas:

1. The meaning of innovation
2. Description of the innovation process with methods and tools
3. Guidelines and digital tools used in the innovation process
4. Identification of knowledge gaps in the innovation process

The meaning of innovation

The first question to be answered for the Gurus was: “*What do you mean by innovation?*”. The motivation to ask this question was to compare the different understandings of innovation among the Gurus and Transfer Lab leaders.

The results show that there is a common understanding of innovation based on multiple terms that were frequently used. The terms mentioned most often to describe what innovation is about are:

- Collaboration, Co-Creation & Open Innovation,
- Creativity,
- Problem solving,
- Adaptive,

⁴ Figure adapted from Diebold & Kofler (2019), *Agilität erlernen? Agilität erleben!*

<https://www.informatik-aktuell.de/management-und-recht/projektmanagement/agilitaet-erlernen-agilitaet-erleben.html>

- Change of perspective,
- User-centred design,
- Sustainable.

Innovation processes and phases

The second question involved the description of the process methodologies or methods or steps followed to develop a project in the lab. With the questions:

- *Do you know any innovation methods? (name them / add a link)*
- *In which phase do you use which method/tool? Try to create a timeline showing your process.*

Many Gurus start the innovation process with a problem that needs to be solved. Thus, the innovation itself must be problem-solving with a change of perspective.

Collaboration, adaptiveness, and creativity are the main competencies required for innovation.

The following quotations from the first exercise show the diversity in innovation concepts, yet the similarities also become clear:

- "Adapted or new solution to a current need."
- "Creating new cross-sectorial exploration that is value driven."
- "Continuous research about the community's interest and needs."
- "Meaningfully improving objects and processes."
- "Find new ways to produce and consume in a more sustainable way."
- "Being adaptive and creative with the problem in hand."

Following this, the phases and methods of the innovation process, as described by the Gurus in the Partner and Transfer Labs, were introduced. Based on the descriptions and aggregated data of all participating labs, a standard process could be identified.

The phases of the standard process were present in almost every innovation process of each lab, with some minor differences. For example, specific labs emphasised additional steps or neglected one aspect of the process. Overall, however, the standard process could be derived from the innovation process shared by each lab. The results show that testing and evaluation often happen simultaneously.

The standard process follows seven phases:

- Phase 1: Identifying the problem
- Phase 2: Ideation
- Phase 3: Conception
- Phase 4: Prototyping
- Phase 5: Testing and evaluation
- Phase 6: Launch

- Phase 7: Documentation

Figure 3. The standard innovation process.

Figure 4 shows whether each lab mentioned the phases of the standard process. Only 13 labs are shown in the diagramme since one participating lab did not specify its innovation process in phases.

Figure 4. Phases of the innovation process per lab.

Guidelines and tools

The third part of the innovation analysis with the shemakes labs was about the guidelines and tools used to support the process. The following questions were asked:

- *Do you have any guidelines or digital tools that support your process? Which ones?*
- *Which sources do you use?*

Table 3 contains the guidelines, websites, toolkits, and other resources used by the labs during the innovation process.

Table 2. Resources used for the innovation process.

Type	Resources used
Websites	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Golden Circle (why-what-how) simonsinek • The Lean Farm by Ben Hartman chelseagreen.com/product/the-lean-farm/ • Atlas of the Future atlasofthefuture.org • Transition Design Framework • transitiondesignseminarcmu.net/wp-content/uploads • Applied DDMI ualresearchonline.arts.ac.uk/id/eprint/13991/ • The Ten circulardesign.org.uk/research/ten/ • The Academy academany.org • Websites like academia.edu for academic research
Books	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning to scale, Regis Medina, 2020 • 9 lies about work, Marcus Buckingham and Ashley Goodall, 2019 • Getting Everything You Can Out of All You've Got: 21 Ways, Jay Abraham, 2001 • E-Myth, Michael E. Gerber, 2004 • Reinventing organisation, Frédéric Laloux, 2015 • Tribes, Seth Godin, 2008
Toolkits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen awareness toolkit making-sense.eu/publication_categories/toolkit • Fab Academy framework fabacademy.org • Reflow governance toolkit
Others	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SISCODE co-creation journey • Active learning pedagogy • CENTRINNO methodology (process by missions x KPIs) • Pinterest for inspiration • Shared governance bioshades model (see TCBL & shemakes) • Textile lab research methodology (see TCBL days) • Collaborative models like sociocracy (see sociocracy network) • archives and documentation/analysis tools) • Hands-on learning

Knowledge gaps

Finally, the innovation analysis workshops aimed to identify knowledge gaps in the innovation process and to increase knowledge transfer among the participating labs.

The related questions for the labs were:

- *Where do you see a lack of knowledge in labs?*
- *Which innovation method would you like to know more about?*

Business advice and best practice examples from other FabLabs are mentioned most often. Table 4 summarises the answers related to the last question.

Table 3. Identified gaps in knowledge of innovation processes.

Type	Knowledge gaps
People, best practice, success stories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examples of projects realised by the FabLabs • Case studies of successful innovation implementation from FabLabs • How to motivate people to engage • Anticipate people turn-overs or team/ individual development
Community and shared information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge and experience sharing between labs (dos and don'ts) • Open-source material innovation databases • Circularity • Shared platform for collaboration • Network for co-creation across disciplines and across countries • Tools for co-creation
Business advice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business training • Business model generation and design + sustainable business models (for FabLabs in particular) • Funding, allocation of budget in FabLabs (staff, machines and others) • How to make the innovation process efficient • Making use of the team canvas • Governance, power distribution, openness in debates, transparency • Sustainability

In the shemakes Open Toolkit there is a section that contains the presentations from the innovation analysis workshops. In addition, it includes a template for the workshop design⁵.

Learnings and next steps

While it was observed that most labs follow a similar approach, the outcome of the innovation process can vary greatly among the labs, ranging from presenting a prototype or a new process to launching a new product with an underlying business plan. Most workshop participants work in a FabLab environment and are not aiming to produce marketable products but instead focus on rapid prototyping activities.

After a documentation phase to analyse the findings of the different innovation processes, the outcome of the innovation analysis was presented to the Gurus and

⁵ The following link contains the presentation and further information of the workshop and results of the innovation analysis <http://fabricademy.fabcloud.io/shemakes/handbook/3-role%20models%20and%20innovation%20narratives/Gurus/3-Innovation%20Analysis/>

the leaders of the Transfer Labs in a general session. Afterwards, the results were disseminated through the shemakes Open Toolkit.

As a next step, further exchange between the leaders of the labs and their teams and the collaborative use of the tools mentioned above is suggested. The implementation of methodologies must be enhanced to foster innovation. The results of the innovation analysis can expand the level of collaboration for the benefit of open innovation. Lab leaders can apply and integrate the standard innovation process to enable further collaboration in the context of the quadruple helix.

The information described in this section is proposed to be applied in further workshops to promote methods of innovation and collaboration in labs. This analysis might be used in a detailed publication on Open Research Europe or other platforms with an open-access policy. The insights of this data will also be used by TCBL, a lab community to empower leaders and managers in labs.

From Gurus to Transfer Tabs

The activity "From Gurus to Transfer Labs" encapsulated the different dynamics of the Gurus involved in the second phase to bring the Gurus and Ambassadors together with the 12 Transfer Labs.

This activity brought a framework of activities and operationalisation of the innovation methodologies and gender vision⁶, together with the new inputs of the Transfer Labs for phase two. This was integrated as part of the biweekly sessions designed for network development (WPI, T1.3). A timeline was established with the participating partner Gurus and Ambassadors, together with the 12 'Transfer' Labs, based on the first steps proposed in D4.2. The timeline was adapted and the activities were reformulated based on input from the biweekly sessions. Here we present an overview of the activities carried out in the last period.

- 1) *Planning the activities* and onboarding session.
- 2) *Starting the transfer of knowledge*, giving guidance and organising the activities.
- 3) *Supporting Ambassadors* and, with the help of MATRIX, enabling exchange with other partners and travel planning.

These sessions enabled a co-creative process, continuing the strategy defined in D 4.2 and the on-boarding activities in collaboration with all labs, to support the

⁶ More information about the the innovation methodology and Innovation ecosystem can be found in the D1.1 shemakes vision https://shemakes.eu/sites/default/files/doc/p/files/su_21oct31_d1.1.pdf

development of all activities with the Partner Labs, Transfer Labs, Gurus and Ambassadors.

Figure 5. Updated timelines with activities from Transfer Labs and Ambassadors.

A detailed overview will be given in the Ambassadors' timeline in the following section. As an example, collaborative work in the first session introduced some questions and used the profile maps to familiarise the Gurus' Ambassadors and transfer in the same Canvas. The following figure shows the presentation of session for the Gurus and Ambassadors.

Figure 6. Interaction Guru- Ambassadors.

In parallel, we detailed the Ambassadors' activities that will also be described below. The Gurus took ownership of the process, such that each Guru and the relevant Task leader interacted with the Transfer Labs and the activity planning, reporting to the biweekly sessions.

3.3. Experience and Feedback

In the following sections we summarise the feedback and experience of each Guru during the second phase.

Nuria (LEON): Curiosity Path

Nuria is the Guru of the LEON lab and was in charge of leading the Curiosity Path task. This task is dedicated to the youngest participants in the project, building on Nuria's experience guiding young makers and girls in the Poderosas project at the LEON lab. In addition, Nuria mentored and accompanied the Ambassadors Carla and Lucia in the experience exchange visits to the respective Transfer Labs, VivaLab In Porto, Portugal, and Decode in Athens, Greece. She acted as a meeting planner and helped them with the activities and documentation. As for the Ambassadors, Nuria guided both girls to fulfil their roles and accompanied them in their travel to the Transfer Labs.

As the coordinator of the children's activities, Nuria had a significant role in promoting their work and involving families and local actors, such as schools, in supporting them. This fact made her work more demanding in terms of time than initially planned, but her commitment to the project and her active participation and concern in supervising the ethical guidelines led to great results. Nuria also presented the work of shemakes at different local and international events.

Activity and results: The e-monster activity was the most replicated workshop among the several labs engaged in the Curiosity Path. Participants learned together to make the e-monsters that were replicated and adapted to the context of the workshop (e.g. paintings at the museum that were very well received by the museum staff).

Reflections: Activities should be adapted to the context, other cultures and countries, and the public, taking into account the circumstances regarding working with minors (e.g. travelling with kids).

Table 4. Gurus' Feedback summary (Nuria).

Aspect	Feedback
Mentoring Ambassadors	<p>Strengths: Lucia and Carla were enthusiastic and "very happy" to share their personal experience with girls in other countries despite their young age. Plus, they appreciated the help they received during the mentoring session, especially Adriana's help.</p> <p>Weaknesses: Carla and Lucia were in school during the Ambassador's meetings, making attendance difficult. Their only difficulty was a lack of autonomy, and they needed to be reminded every time what to do.</p>

Aspect	Feedback
Mentoring Transfer Labs	Strengths: The Transfer Labs showed similar interests, which made the mission for Nuria easier, and since they were able to find active stakeholders, the Ambassadors could conduct their activities easily. Weaknesses: There were some issues regarding ethics with minors, leading to issues and delays in the relation between the Transfer Labs and the different institutions. This led to difficulties in planning the activities and completing the documentation.
Co-creation tools and values	Transfer Labs: Together, they made a collection of new activities and this created new opportunities for the future. Ambassadors: They succeed in being role models and an inspiration for the girls at their age in the lab. They want to pursue their relationship with the Transfer Labs.
Pair and teamwork	During the project, Adrian (a new Ambassador selected in the 2nd call) has been supporting and working in close collaboration with Nuria, mainly in editing the videos and documentation of the activities. In the second phase, with the welcoming of the male gender to the project, Adrian was nominated and proclaimed as Ambassador, and travelled with the shemakes flag to the International Fab event in Bali.
Conclusions	During the project, shemakes was an opportunity to learn with others, especially with children and young people, not only about textiles and technology but also about other cultures and other ways to make things. During the second phase, LEON established a strong relationship with the Transfer Labs, mainly with Vivalab. Due to the proximity of the two cities (Leon and Porto) and the Ambassadors, the two labs will continue their collaboration in the learning activities with the Ambassadors as new mentors for the next generation of children in textile and tech.

Anastasia (IAAC): Lab-to-Lab Project on wool

Anastasia is the Guru from IAAC, and together with Marion Real, lead the WP2 Learning Paths as well as Task 3.3 “Lab to Lab projects” dedicated to three research projects within the general theme of wool. As co-founder of Fabricademy and the FabTextiles collective, Anastasia gave significant input to the Partner and Transfer Labs and mentored Ambassadors Petra and Tasnim as well as two Transfer Labs: the Icelandic Textile Centre (ICT) in Blönduós, Iceland and the Textile Prototyping Lab (TPL) in Berlin, Germany. As a Guru, she guided the Transfer Labs through the content and activities of shemakes and inspired them with best practices, methodologies and shared infrastructure. She also consulted them on the best way to spend their budget and supported them in building up and equipping their lab for hosting activities. Her role

was also to connect the labs with innovations in textiles and clothing and with experts in the field. In addition to the two assigned labs (TPL and ICT), she also accompanied Farmlab in building their lab inventory, consumables and research. She also helped Ziphouse and Roglab by suggesting experts for conducting activities according to their topics of interest. Anastasia mentored the Ambassadors and enabled meaningful conversations in planning the content and logistics during the activity planning and guidance of the Ambassador's exchanges.

Concrete actions: Discussion and mentoring content creation with the Ambassadors led to a definition of the full schedule of activities, ensured the production of communication material and helped promote the activities and document results in the shemakes Open Toolkit.

Activity and results: Many workshops held at the ICT were open to the public, and new participants had the opportunity to learn about the textile lab and get new skills that combine technology and textiles. The ICT had the opportunity to reach out and connect with a local biology research centre and establish collaborations with the university and TPL for workshops implemented in the curricula.

Reflections: There is a need for training the labs and the Ambassadors on how to document their activities.

Takeaways: Many of the labs are new and they are still in the process of building their identity and audience. For this reason, it is essential to communicate the activities in advance and try to reach out to a larger public by collaborating with media that can disseminate the activities to have a greater impact.

Table 5. Gurus' Feedback summary (Anastasia)

Aspect	Feedback
Mentoring Ambassadors	<p>Strengths: While mentoring, Petra and Tasnim both showed excellence in their contribution and leadership. In addition, their independence and drive made the mission easier for the Gurus. Both Tasnim and Petra are Fabricademy alumni, so they had previous experience with the content and the open source methodology of Fabricademy and how to document and organise workshops.</p> <p>Weaknesses: Overall, it would have been better to have more time to plan and organise all activities in shemakes.</p>
Mentoring Transfer Labs	<p>Strengths: The trust and recommendations of the Gurus led to successful mentoring of the Transfer Tabs, allowing them to implement their activities and adapt them to the local context.</p> <p>Weaknesses: As concerns the organisation of the workshops, there was a discrepancy in how the budget was combined with the limited time for conducting the activities due to covid restrictions and the project</p>

Aspect	Feedback
	<p>timeline. It would have been beneficial to have a budget plan overview, to include some budget for attending meetings and to understand the best practices for spending the budget.</p>
<p>Co-creation tools and values</p>	<p>Transfer Labs: The networking approach and the collaborative nature of the shemakes project have led to the creation of specific collaborations between labs for the future.</p> <p>Ambassadors: The Ambassadors created a network of innovators of excellence and seeded future opportunities for them.</p>
<p>Pair and teamwork</p>	<p>The IAAC Guru has an inspirational role in the shemakes networks due to her role in Fabricademy and was a key contact for both Transfer Labs and Ambassadors. Anastasia co-designed with labs, supported Ambassadors with content and organisational procedures, shared career opportunities within a vision for sustaining global cooperation. In IAAC, cooperation was consolidated during the shemakes project. Marion Real supported Anastasia Pistofidou mainly for envisioning/designing as well as in the coordination of tasks and reports. While contributing to both, Anastasia led WP2 Learning Paths while Marion was actively involved in the running of the Wool projects, still leaving many opportunities for dialogues and engagement.</p>
<p>Conclusions:</p>	<p>Shemakes was an important experience to continue, expand and distribute roles within textile labs. The role of Guru has been in the DNA of Anastasia for years, and she was able to continue this through shemakes, onboarding new members and seeing Ambassadors becoming more autonomous and engaged in the community. The wool projects and collaborations illustrated well why and how labs could synchronise their research efforts in one topic and contribute within a peer learning mindset to address societal challenges. They hope this can continue in the future.</p>

Cristina and Shannon (ONLF): Discovery Path

Cristina and Shannon are the Gurus from ONLF. Under their mentorship were Andrea and Diana as Ambassadors. They mentored the Transfer Labs VIVISTOP Lab in Užupis, Lithuania and the Green Fabric in Brussels, Belgium. While Cristina had a representative role in the first phase and accompanied Shannon in the conception of the Activities, Shannon took the leadership of the second phase guiding the Transfer Labs and Ambassadors and having exchanges with further collaborations.

This team of Gurus succeeded in driving their appointed lab in their preparation of activities through their regular meetings together. They provided them with assistance in on-set activities and documentation.

Activity and results: They had a successful experience with the Ambassadors on the one hand and with the Transfer Labs on the other, new and content-adapted activities. These activities have been adapted from the content, format, and type of collaboration they had with different stakeholders.

Reflections: Since they had a narrow time frame, they couldn't develop a plan on how to integrate the subject of gender into the activities. Despite this, all the Transfer Labs did an "excellent" job adapting the activities.

Takeaways: Each Transfer Lab now has the opportunity to continue collaborating with the stakeholders, run new activities and have a shemakes network to rely on. They can also seek new collaboration with the experience of shemakes under their belt.

Table 6. Gurus' feedback summary (Cristina/Shannon)

Aspect	Feedback
Mentoring Ambassadors	<p>Strengths: Overall, it was noted that both Ambassadors were quite responsive, and they enjoyed their experience. They got the chance to widen their circle of acquaintance since they are still in contact with the Transfer Lab.</p> <p>One of the Ambassadors was able to teach her class at the Transfer Lab, and it was included in the 3-day activities. This Ambassador is a teacher for fashion students back home and introduced new techniques such as thermo dye and e-textiles, which the students had never used before and mixed in techniques they knew, such as draping.</p> <p>Weaknesses: An unmatched time schedule: One of the Ambassadors couldn't join all the Wednesday meetings because of work.</p>
Mentoring Transfer Labs	<p>Strengths: The mentoring from both sides was enthusiastic and successful. All labs were "very responsive, very independent, and "very well organised" on filling slides and documentation, and they successfully found new stakeholders in their labs.</p> <p>Weaknesses: However, there were some flaws. There was confusion on some of the guidelines and some even had difficulty introducing the subject of gender into the activities. On the other hand, there were some problems with the time; there wasn't enough time to prepare the evaluation for the activities.</p>
Co-creation tools and values	<p>Transfer Labs: With this experience, the Transfer Lab was able to try new activities. It allowed them to widen their network with new connections with the universities and other stakeholders. This would enable them to grow as labs in the future.</p> <p>The One to One meeting was the best way to get familiar with each other after knowing what activities to do. It was shared that they had different kinds of meetings: Every lab, Discovery lab, One to One.</p> <p>Ambassadors: It opened an opportunity for one of the Ambassadors; she is going to continue teaching the Transfer Lab online.</p>

Aspect	Feedback
Pair and teamwork	<p>At the beginning of the project, Cristina was a Guru and was in charge of the shemakes project. Shannon was introduced a few months after the project started. A procedure was put in place: Shannon would assist with the meetings and online workshops while Cristina would have a more background role.</p> <p>During phase 1, both worked together to delegate and transition the responsibilities of Cristina to Shannon but both would work on the different workshops.</p> <p>During phase 2, Shannon took the responsibility to work with the Transfer Labs for the discovery path. Which led to the decision on Shannon becoming Onl'fait's Guru instead of Cristina because of her role in the frontline of the project.</p>
Conclusions	<p>Before the project, Onl'fait knew and worked with some of the labs and actors that are participating in shemakes, such as WAAG, IAAC and LEON. The expectation of Onl'fait was to reinforce these connections and collaborate within the shemakes network. Additionally, these collaborations would also be the chance to learn and inspire one another.</p> <p>The shemakes project gave Onl'fait the opportunity to create collaboration with the students from the local art university and museums, but mostly it gave that same opportunity to the Transfer Labs.</p> <p>A big highlight was seeing how the Ambassadors learned skills with Onl'fait activities in phase 1. Then, they taught it in the Transfer Labs in phase 2. The same goes for the activities adapted from phases 1 to 2 in different labs. Which enables the knowledge to grow, but so does the network.</p> <p>The future would be a continuation of this process. A growing network and the people who learned would then teach by recreating, adapting, and bringing their new parts. This will enable us to continue the collaboration and be able to learn from one another and see our knowledge grow and adapt in different contexts and cultures.</p>

Andreea and Elvys (REDU): Community Engagement

Andreea and Elvys were the Team Guru from REDU. They were in charge of the Community Engagement task, which focuses on engaging with local communities to identify and address issues related to gender and opportunity structures. They mentored the Ambassadors Marilena and Alexandra and the Transfer Labs Centre for Circular Design in London, United Kingdom and Lottozero Textile Laboratories in Prato, Italy. Throughout the process of mentoring the Ambassadors and the Transfer Labs, Andreea and Elvys encouraged and supported them, organising discussions for both parties to make sure they got familiarised with and had better knowledge and

understanding of the activities. They started by planning meetings with all four labs together.

Activity and results: Transfer Labs adapted various activities to their context. By working closely with the Transfer Labs, a learning process unfolded to discover new communities and learn new ways of interacting with them. REDU and the Transfer Lab teams, regardless of their experience or background, were able to expand and diversify their communities, creating essential links with relevant key stakeholders.

Reflections: It was considered to be an intense experience that they all would love to be able to do it again.

Takeaways: The shemakes project made them grow enormously and learn to go beyond their limits and build together this community that they hope will continue to grow beautifully.

Table 7. Gurus' Feedback summary (Andreea/Elvys).

Aspect	Feedback
Mentoring the Ambassadors	Strengths: Each Ambassador provided great help with their contribution, co-development, presence, experience and involvement in the activities. Weaknesses: Problems with time.
Mentoring the Transfer Labs	Strengths: The new labs were highly responsive in developing the activities and especially bringing valuable input into improving them. Intensive work has been done based on mutual trust on both sides. Weaknesses: Not having enough time to be prepared in terms of developing the activities or being fully integrated into the shemakes community.
Co-creation tools and values	Transfer Labs: The co-creation process was eventually adapted to the way of working of each Transfer Lab. Variations on the initial tools (Miro) have been used according to the experience with these kinds of tools and the capacities and the needs of each lab. The most significant output from this experience is the set of connections that will certainly lead to future collaborations. Ambassadors: They provided significant support and adaptability. One or both could well get the chance to collaborate with REDU in future activities and projects.
Pair and teamwork	In terms of gender, the REDU team is a mixed one, with Andreea and Elvys both acting as Gurus. When the shemakes project started, the two had already been working together for about four years. Perhaps it was the fact that they only worked in small teams (maximum eight people) that helped them work so well together. They consider themselves privileged that the people they attract

Aspect	Feedback
	<p>around them have the same values and principles as they do. Perhaps because of this, they were surprised by the reality outside their bubble, which can sometimes seem hard to deal with. Through their activities in shemakes they discovered together the perception of the gender gap in the Romanian textile industry, interacted with key people in the textile sector and co-opted them in this approach to reduce the gender gap. The two believe that they have discovered/rediscovered people but also themselves, especially in relation to the female part of the industry. Elvys' presence has always helped in our events, being very open and gentle and, it seems, giving the women confidence to see that there are reliable men who are aware and concerned about reducing the gender gap.</p> <p>Their way of working is one where they complement each other, where they build ideas together and debate them until they are both happy with the result and feel confident that they have developed something feasible and impactful.</p>
<p>Conclusions</p>	<p>Before the start of the project, the REDU team had the experience of having collaborated in another project (TCBL) with WAAG and IAAC. The shemakes project offered them the opportunity to ground and expand these links through a very close and friendly collaboration. They analysed and absorbed the methodology from the first phase and passed it on in the same way to Transfer Labs.</p> <p>The REDU team sees the whole experience as a process of learning and adapting to each other's needs and to the problems and needs of the community around each Transfer Lab. They perceive the shemakes network as a stable and relevant one, which has a strong chance of remaining active in the long term, thanks primarily to the compatibility and collaboration between the labs.</p>

Cecilia and Beatriz (WAAG): Innovation path

Cecilia Raspanti and Beatriz Sandini are the team Gurus from WAAG, Cecilia is the leader of WP3 innovation Services, and they also guide Task 2.3 Innovation Path.

Cecilia and Beatriz mentored the Ambassadors Jessica and Irene and the Transfer Labs of RogLab in Ljubljana Slovenia and the Farm lab in Kapfenstein, Austria.

Beatriz's input and her vision of entrepreneurship helped to organise the activities at the beginning of the project, particularly in the first phase. Cecilia, who had already been building the TCBL and Fabricademy ecosystem, contributed to the understanding and mission orientation of shemakes. An essential element of knowledge transfer was the in depth contribution to the lab to lab research project with IAAC and the other participating labs. In addition, the team contributed to the integration of the lab profiles and the operationalisation of the values of the shemakes

project. These contributions to the shemakes vision helped deepen the integration and reflection of the values in the activities and the mission of reputation management .

Activity and results: Cecilia and Beatriz supported activities where women felt not alone and wanted to be seen or be an inspiration for their unconventional career paths. The labs connected to their territory and began to attract women from there.

The hands-on activities were divided into Innovation Path and Business Engagement for different reasons.

Reflections: It was an experience that they would like to do again .

Takeaways: The entire experience was a good example of how to value the network driven by women and the role of supportive men.

Table 8. Gurus' Feedback summary (Cecilia/Beatriz),

Aspect	Feedback
Mentoring Ambassadors	<p>Strengths: Jessica was very driven, organised, taking the initiative and independent. She had a good, clear team communication and was easy to collaborate with. Irene was energetic by nature (despite that many things came in between). Cecilia added that she “fully” embodied the shemakes project, values and attitude, which was a “huge” plus; “Her self reflective nature, kindness and strength also very much matched the shemakes ways. So both ways are a great fit. She has a strong vision of women's leadership, and knowledge of unconventional examples of excellence too. She is an exceptional Ambassador, I believe.”</p> <p>Weaknesses: Due to personal issues, Irene couldn't travel; first covid at the lab, then Irene's family health, then her own personal condition.</p>
Mentoring Transfer Labs	<p>Strengths: It was easy to work and collaborate with them and, more importantly, to share information with them. The Transfer Lab teams were very driven to learn more, to the point that sometimes mentoring was more than expected, leading to additional in-depth meetings. Some labs needed more mentoring than others (Ziphouse), while other labs were mentored for certain tasks.</p> <p>Farmlab had a “great” reflection and made “an incredible adaptation to their local context”. The team was not able to directly mentor Roglab but knowing how they value community engagement, Jessica in the Ambassador role was able to provide sufficient support.</p> <p>Weaknesses: Not having enough time for the preparation even to do things spontaneously. One of the labs (Ziphouse) had some difficulties engaging with one of the target groups; survey, mentoring and giving business advice.</p>
Co-creation of	Transfer Labs: The Transfer Labs complained about some of the tools, in

Aspect	Feedback
tools and values	<p>particular: "Miro as a tool was heavy to use" due to slow loading and interactivity. The slides prepared by the Gurus were very well received however. Some were grateful for the simple process, while others had difficulties with the activities. They didn't understand what to do in response to their network (Ziphouse) but they got help from other labs (REDU).</p> <p>Ambassadors: They didn't have issues with the values and working with the tools, especially Jessica, who is creative by nature and embodied the values.</p>
Pair and teamwork	<p>In terms of the split of tasks between both Gurus, there were different moments of engagement in the shemakes activities. During the first year and phase, both Cecilia and Beatriz were involved, co-creating with the Core Labs and designing the first phase of activities. Due to Beatriz's maternity leave, she was not present when the Transfer Labs and Ambassadors joined the project, so Cecilia took the lead. They worked together, sharing their knowledge in their field of expertise and mainly bringing in the experience of working at Fabricademy, where distributed and collaborative methods are already applied.</p>
Conclusions:	<p>Having the role of a Guru gave them space to share their knowledge and at the same time lead other labs or women involved in different perspectives and paths. The meetings and activities allowed this to happen in a fluid way and the connections made will continue to benefit the lab as it expands its networks and possible future collaborations.</p>

Victor (MAKE): Business Engagement

Victor Senave was the Guru from makesense. He led Task 3.4 Business Engagement, working with labs in researching their local contexts to focus on solving challenges of local women entrepreneurs. He mentored the Ambassadors Camille and Melanie and the Textile Lab in Lyon, France and the Ziphouse Design Hub in Chişinău, Moldova. During his mentorship, he played the role of facilitator between the different actors to ensure a smooth connection, through weekly meetings and one to one sessions.

Activity and results: They started from the activities tested in the first phase but then the process allowed them to develop adaptations of the initial activities and new activities bringing a new dimension to the final model – engaging more of the community of entrepreneurs and sharing good practice between labs and Ambassadors.

Reflections: Victor says it was not always easy to understand the context of everyone, but it was “a good experience” to connect at the human level to other actors defending the same dream.

Takeaways: As a Guru, the experience has given him more theory about how to make change, a better understanding and knowledge of the T&C ecosystem, and pride in taking part in his first project with such a global scope.

Table 9. Gurus' Feedback summary (Victor).

Aspect	Feedback
Mentoring Ambassadors	<p>Strengths: Makesense has been training and supporting entrepreneurs for a long time now, so they have resources and knowledge to share.</p> <p>Weaknesses: The war in Ukraine made planning more difficult. Also, the differences in culture sometimes made support more difficult as Victor did not have a good understanding of the real barriers towards entrepreneurship in countries other than France.</p>
Mentoring Transfer Labs	<p>Strengths: For makesense, already working with and trusting Camille, it was easy to launch themselves in this adventure – starting from broad objectives and then empowering Camille to achieve them with the labs. It was a real learning experience for both parts.</p> <p>Weaknesses: It was sometimes difficult to get answers from Melanie, plus the fact that she couldn't go to Moldavia for obvious reasons made the connection harder between her and her lab.</p>
Co-creation tools and values	<p>Transfer Labs: Co-creating with the labs was at the core of the project as everything started with a set of activities, and then modifying and adding to this set after brainstorming together. The values always ought to be seen as a framework to develop activities and tools. It can all be seen in the final online kit.</p> <p>Ambassadors: Co-creating with the Ambassadors was less concrete. However, in the onboarding process for the Ambassadors, the shemakes values took a lot of space and were central when supporting the labs they were assigned to.</p>
Pair and teamwork	<p>After having the role passed on from Olympe to Victor, throughout the whole project, he has been working with different pairs: Clervie, Eleonore and Salome.</p> <p>At makesense, they have a model inspired by holocracy and do not practice classical hierarchical organisation, so working together took a lot of different forms: brain partnering, separation of tasks depending on the activities, etc.</p> <p>One clear separation was made, though: Victor being the direct contact for Transfer Labs and Salome being the lead on activities.</p>
Conclusions	<p>Before shemakes, makesense did not really collaborate much with the T&C sector, but taking part in such an experience helped open this new</p>

Aspect

Feedback

environment in which makesense has a lot to bring through its entrepreneurship, civic engagement and collaboration activities. Makesense's Guru, Victor, leaves this experience with better keys to collaboration.

3.4. Conclusions

The Gurus were at the core of each project activity, as sources of technology transfer and business know-how and motivators and promoters of the shemakes values. In this chapter, we have described their involvement in the project, their dedication and contribution and their strategic role in accompanying the implementation of the second phase of shemakes. The results of the activities demonstrate the significant work and efforts that each of them made in supporting the lab leaders, the Ambassadors, and constant communication in the team. It also demonstrated the strong collaborative approach of the lab teams.

Considering the time constraints and the difficulties of managing the labs and logistics in real-life scenarios, and considering that the development of their role took place during a pandemic, we highlighted the strengths of the Gurus in carrying out the planned activities.

They recommended and supervised the selection of the second round of Ambassadors together with the Transfer Lab leaders. This process enabled a second expansion of ideas and development of leaders in the local communities.

In the final months, the Gurus focused on documentation and the consolidation of the Open Toolkit repository to allow the dissemination and growth of the shemakes community after the end of the project. During the Final Conference, they contributed with their input during the shemakes journey, sharing their testimony and giving visibility to their efforts.

4. Ambassadors

Ambassadors are girls, young women and women innovators who participated in shemakes.eu activities in WPs 2 and 3, proving the capacity to emerge as leaders and 'carry the message' to their peers in other cultural and geographical contexts, thus acting as a multiplier mechanism for the shemakes.eu network.

This section describes the activities of the first group of Ambassadors. The activities and tools are presented, introducing the practical logistics and content development supported by the Gurus, Transfer Lab leaders and consortium partners. In particular, we give an overview of the first Ambassador's experience of exchanging and carrying out their activities in the Transfer Labs.

From M18, WP4 began to plan the second call for Ambassadors, presenting the selection and opportunities for exchange and expansion.

4.1. Activities Carried Out

The activities of the Transfer Labs and Ambassadors were carried out and co-created in parallel with the consortium partners. In this chapter, we present an overview of the activities that took place in the second phase, especially for the participation of the first-call Ambassadors.

From the very beginning of their involvement, WP4 was keen to understand the objectives and reasons the Ambassadors sought to achieve through their role. To this end, tools were developed during this process to create routines and habits and build small changes.

- To gradually change their perceptions and to create belonging and confidence among the Ambassadors.
- To feel confident to prepare their ideas and present them in public.
- To have their own reflections through experience.
- To be observers and to be able to understand new contexts.
- To reflect and present upon the activities in their local contexts to share them back to the network and the global shemakes community.
- To grow their network and contacts.

The table on the following page presents an overview of the sessions carried out.

Table 10. Timeline of activities for first call Ambassadors.

Stage	Date	Meeting type
Connecting and exploring	19-20 January	Kick-off Plenary session Shemakes Partner Labs, Transfer Labs, and Ambassadors connecting each other and exploring the shemakes ecosystem.
Preparing	02 February	Activities Discussion Plenary session Gender Vision Debrief profile map and agenda
	16 February	Activities Discussion Plenary session Guidelines Activity / Group Ambassadors session sketchbook
	28 -february	Gift challenge Group Ambassadors session
	Week 28 – 1 march	INTERIM MEETINGS One-to-one Session (20 minutes each) Ambassador, Guru and Transfer Lab planning activity.
Doing	16 Marsh	Drop-in sessions I Open session to share your plans, discuss details and doubts. These sessions are planned to fine-tune your activity plan.
	30 March	
	27 April	
Documenting	04 May	Drop-in sessions II Open session Drop-in sessions are available for feedback and documentation questions.
	09 June	FINAL Recap presentation: 9 Jun Group Ambassadors session Presentation of results and preparation plenary session
Celebrating	22 June	Plenary session Open public presentation of results of the Ambassadors and Transfer Labs

Folloing is a brief overview of the content that WP4 introduced to the Ambassadors.

Gender Vision

Ambassadors and Transfer Labs received input on the gender vision and the values to disseminate as Ambassadors, using a storytelling dynamic led by Tavistock and incorporating online co-creation tools.

Figure 7. Gender Vision workshop with Ambassadors II.

Group session

This activity introduced sharing and planning and getting feedback from all Ambassadors. The meeting was an opportunity to hear what others were doing and to discuss ideas with each other during the bi-weekly meetings.

Gift Weave Challenge

This format, described in D4.2, made in the presence of the Gurus reflects on their role and contribution as a “gift” in the project. This activity was carried out with online participation of the Ambassadors, reflecting on the “gift” and hearing their voices on how each Ambassador contributes to the network⁷.

This format was described in the previous D4.2. Reputation Interim Report, which tells the format and results of the activity carried out on-site with the Gurus during the consortium meeting in Barcelona. For the first Ambassadors, the format is slightly changed to a digital format, keeping the same exploration of building a community that weaves strong networks.

Figure 8. The tangible gift weave challenge.

⁷ Further documentation of this activity can be found in the Open Toolkit Gift weave challenge <http://fabricademy.fabcloud.io/shemakes/handbook/3.-reputation%20management/3.%20Ambassadors/2.-Gift%20weave%20Challenge/>

Figure 9. The gift weave challenge co-creation board with the first round Ambassadors.

Lessons learned

Although everything was done online, the Ambassadors were able to share their own stories about their experiences and how they could help each other through the skills they have. They presented the kind of contributions they could make, from teaching to their passion for technology, science and exploration of new challenges. In addition, each Ambassador offered a “gift” to motivate the others and to transmit their passion for the project with some of their stories:

- “You learn from your past mistakes.”
- “Doing this activity is taking me out of my comfort zone.”
- “Analysing and understanding a situation is the foundation of my actions.”
- “Lack of knowledge can motivate you.”
- “Enthusiasm and empathy can go a long way to empower people!”
- “Away to lead collectively with courage and kindness.”

This exercise aimed to encourage Ambassadors to think as individuals and further clarify their contribution in their role. They then presented their gift to the others, to provide a room of confidence and to self-reflect by sharing experiences.

- **One-to-one sessions:** Prior to these one-on-one sessions, all the Ambassadors were asked to complete a short interim plan, including: an activity canvas presentation/ sketchbook, planning with Transfer Labs and a brief reflection of the challenges and opportunities in the process.

Figure 10. Sessions with the Guru Transfer Lab leaders from RogLab, Community engagement. Fab lab León Guru and Ambassadors Curiosity

- **Drop-in sessions:** Adriana, as WP4 Leader, and the Gurus were available in an online meeting to drop in and ask questions or discuss their project.
- **Recap and feedback:** This session was planned to review and share results. In the feedback sessions, it was possible to understand the opportunities for improvement and desires for the further development of the community.
- **Opportunity and visibility slots:** These sessions, supported by TCBL and Fabricademy, enabled the visibility and further connection of all Ambassadors and presented their work during Fabricademy and TCBL conferences and events.

4.2. Tools and methods

Building tools and a methodological framework that reflect on how to grow in the role of Ambassadors was important for the accompaniment of Ambassadors. Therefore, as well as WP2 and WP3, we share some of the tools that have been documented in the Open Toolkit.

Open Toolkit: Role models and innovation narratives

As described in D3.4 “Innovation services Final Toolkit”, the shemakes Open Toolkit has been created as a digital documentation system for shemakes Labs to exchange knowledge, organising a shared set of tools that support the creation of an enabling environment for women. Its form, shape, size and relevance grew with the project, clearly representing the intensive collaboration between all Labs in a open-access repository.

As an outcome, Labs produced a robust multi-purpose toolkit that, in the context of the shemakes project, guided the Transfer Labs on how to situate themselves and , in this case, also guide the Ambassadors in their role to adopt and adapt methods and tools to their local challenges for gender equality and empowerment of women.

Ambassadors could also contribute to the toolkit as it became the ultimate documentation, with a set of tools and guidelines capturing the knowledge acquired by the shemakes community. The labs were identified as the primary igniters of change. The section “Role models and innovation narratives” was introduced to gather information from WP4 that could be relevant for further use, in particular, for Ambassadors to guide and find the necessary resources.

Figure 11. Open Toolkit Role models and innovation narratives.

Co-creative Boards⁸

In principle, we had an online meeting to enable the interaction of all partners and connect the Ambassadors with the Transfer Labs and Gurus. WP4 developed online co-creation boards for the Ambassador's activities and sketchbooks. This format was used as their framework to share different ideas. The Ambassadors, Gurus and the respective actors could teach and spread the message of shemakes worldwide and overcome constraints on in-person activities, particularly due to the pandemic.

Sketchbooks

The Sketchbooks, as the name suggests, compile sketches and notes to support the journey of the Ambassadors. The sketchbooks started with building a better understanding of the task and then allow to document the process from the beginning of their role as Ambassadors. Every Ambassador was handed a personal sketchbook during their mission to spread the shemakes' vision and adapt the content in the Transfer Labs of twelve different countries. This tool allows Ambassadors to follow activities, particularly for the benefit of those that couldn't attend the sessions, and to reflect on and explore their own journey. The sketchbook is also designed for use off-line.

⁸ <https://www.mural.co/>

Dear shemakes Ambassadors

We know that being an innovator is something that is built day by day...

Just like becoming a scientist or an entrepreneur, all these paths can be initiated and strengthened from a young age, cultivated at university and developed and supported as professionals.

We want to be your community!

We want to support you in the process of building your ideas for a more sustainable fashion industry together with the shemakes community of future female innovators. Remember that your ideas and your experiences are part of the larger shemakes innovation ecosystem. This notebook is made to help you in that process.

All the best,
The shemakes team

Figure 12. Welcoming Ambassadors to the sketchbooks.

The sketchbooks aim to offer Ambassadors two points of view:

- *"The messenger"* is the person to carry the spirit of shemakes. Values and practices are a message for communication and reflection.
- *"The observer"* monitors Transfer Labs' practices and identifies how to implement the values in their experience as an Ambassador.

The general structure contains 1) schedules, 2) reminders, 3) a call for action, including takeaways, and 4) a checklist for the next steps.

WP4 produced four Sketchbooks following the different stages of the timeline and adapting it for the kind of activity accompanying the transition of the labs and travel. The following paragraphs will introduce the sketchbooks 1) Gender Vision, 2) activity planning for 2.1). Learning Paths and 2.2). Innovation Services and 3) Experience in the Transfer Lab.

Sketchbook Gender Vision⁹

In the Gender Vision sketchbook, WP4 expands the conversation of the online session on the shemakes vision. Here, the Ambassadors reflected on their personal experiences and then wrote down their points of view concerning the shemakes values. The aim here is to ensure that the Ambassadors would spread the shemakes values with a successful exchange between the local and global communities.

The figure below illustrates how Ambassadors contribute their personal reflections on needs, barriers and frustration while interacting on the collective level and suggesting solutions. As the first sketchbook, the idea was to invite Ambassadors to create the habit of taking notes during the project and to explore how, individually and collectively, we can achieve change.

Figure 13. Carla's reflections (Curiosity Path Ambassador).

The figure below describes some reflections and takeaways from the online session and an open invitation to reflect on how to apply them and create further conversation in the community during the meetings and the activities in the Transfer Labs.

⁹More details on this Sketchbook can be found here:

<http://fabricademy.fabcloud.io/shemakes/handbook/3.->

[role%20models%20and%20voices/Ambassadors/Sketchbooks/1-Gender%20vision/](http://fabricademy.fabcloud.io/shemakes/handbook/3.-role%20models%20and%20voices/Ambassadors/Sketchbooks/1-Gender%20vision/)

Your takeaway from the shemakes gender vision

Before you start, write down what do you identify with or what would you like to change about this vision?

Figure 14. Marilena's takeaways from the gender vision (Community Engagement Ambassador).

Figure 15. Camille's notes on the value Equal (Business Engagement Ambassador).

Sketchbook Activity planning

These Sketchbooks were mainly designed to accompany activity planning as the range of activities and targets was very diverse; WP4 developed two sketchbooks to support activities in WP2 Learning paths and WP3 Innovation services.

Activity planning Learning paths¹⁰

The learning paths accompany hands-on workshops or planning a series of group activities. It was designed:

- To teach Ambassadors practical skills, techniques or ideas to implement in their journey in the Transfer Lab.
- To prepare Ambassadors for the role of leading, e.g to overcome the fear of speaking in public, providing tips and resources to prepare for delivery.
- To function as a tool of communication and discussion with the Gurus and Transfer Labs. This allowed Ambassadors to share their ideas and questions during the one-on-one sessions.

This Sketchbook also allows to document the experience in the shemakes Open Toolkit. It supports the following content:

- **PLANNING:** What are your workshops' objectives?
- **PREPARATION:** What do you need to prepare and what do you need for the workshop?
- **A WELL-STRUCTURED AGENDA:** What will you do in your workshop and when will you do that?

Planning

Define the objective of your Workshop:

Workshop 1: The main objective of this workshop is to explore different concepts related to the basics of building soft circuits and wearables using e-textiles materials and TPL modular kit to make interesting interactive textile projects.

Workshop 2 (Open - Hybrid): The main objective of this workshop is to use cross stitching embroidery art to make interactive art pieces using special e-textile fibers and conductive yarns. Cross stitching is particularly chosen as it is an art that work with concepts highly related to coding/ programming specially in terms of the overall architecture. The workshop is targeting to share inspiring thoughts through artistic interactive pieces while learning the basics of soft circuits. Reflecting on this performing art, the multicolor and cross stitches symbolizes the beauty of embracing diversity and unity.

What do you want to do to guide participants through the experience?

Workshop 1: I want the participants to build interesting wearable products as projects for their Garment Technology course.

Workshop 2: I want the participants to make interactive swatches using cross stitching. During the workshop session, the time and material will be addressing cross stitching as a traditional technique for embroidery and how can smart fibers be used to make interactive embroidered pieces.

After the workshop, it will be additional task to add artistic touches to the pieces to share their values, inspiring stories, and driving quotes.

What do you hope they will learn from it?

To get started with e-textiles and how to embed them within regular textiles to get inspired by the amazing fabric and the impact made of the smart materials to build interactive garments that can be more than just a piece of clothing.

Learn how to cross stitch interactive art pieces for display.

Know Your Topic!

Feel confident! Do some research on your topic and be prepared for questions (you don't have to know everything).

Know Your Participants!

- Understand them and their needs.
- What do they already know?
- What is their field?
- Do they know one another/or work together?
- Are you introducing a new concept or method that conflicts with what they have been doing or their previous training?
- Under what circumstances are they attending this workshop?

Consider the number of participants!

With 8-12 participants you can arrange small group activities (2-4) and individual activities. With more than 12 participants you might need to split the group.

Consider how much time you have

Remember: For participants with little knowledge you should give more time for questions, operations etc.

- Rehearse different parts of your workshop to save time being there.
- Keep in mind people might not be there a full hour and fifteen minutes.
- Plan a backup.
- Always reflect on the amount of material you can present (how much information can people absorb in a specific amount of time).
- Allow some time for participants to get to know each other, exchange ideas etc.

Figure 16. Objectives workshop (Discovery Ambassadors).

¹⁰ More details on this Sketchbook can be found here:

<http://fabricademy.fabcloud.io/shemakes/handbook/3.-role%20models%20and%20voices/Ambassadors/Sketchbooks/3.-Preparation%20for%20the%20activity/1.-Learning%20Paths/>

Workshop 2: Smart Stitches Open Workshop

Create a well-structured

Agenda

List the skills and/or topics you will cover
Move the most important information to the early part of the workshop

2nd May 2022		
Time	Activity	Ask yourself
14:00 - 14:15	Introduction	
14:15 - 15:30	Cross stitching art: history, using the art for textile narratives and analogy with coding. Getting Started with smart stitches - Demonstration on the showcase projects	<p>1 Which exercises and methods are best suited for the task at hand?</p>
15:30 - 15:40	Coffee Break	
16:40 - 17:30	Hands On: Making your own interactive cross stitched art piece.	<p>1 How to design an interactive cross stitched art piece?</p>
17:30 - 17:50	Presenting the outcomes	<p>1 Is there enough time for every task?</p>
17:50 - 18:00	Closure	

Preparation

What I need for the workshop?
Where will the workshop take place?
Do you need to set up the room?
Do you need a screen or a whiteboard?
Do you need markers, post-its etc.?

The workshop will take place at the Textile Prototyping Lab in Fraunhofer IZM.

I need:

- Display screen
- White board and markers
- White papers and pencils or pens
- Electronics tool kit

Which materials do you need? Does the Transfer Lab have all the materials you need?

Yes, TPL have purchased and prepared the electronics tool kit.
I will bring some showcase switches for demonstration and guide (to be printed before hand).

Which machines do you need? Does the Transfer Lab have all the machines you need?

Figure 17. Tasnims' 2nd-day schedule and preparation for the Smart Stitches workshop.

Activity planning Innovation Services¹¹

This sketchbook, co-created with WP3 partners, promotes the actions that a lab performs to connect with its context for research and innovation, while enabling its layered community.

There are three levels:

- **Community level:** engaging with the local lab community, raising awareness, and creating a safe space for discussion.
- **Research level:** in-depth hands-on research and knowledge transfer.
- **Business level:** new collaborations: exchange of knowledge, co-creation.

¹¹ More details on this Sketchbook can be found here:

<http://fabricademy.fabcloud.io/shemakes/handbook/3.-role%20models%20and%20voices/Ambassadors/Sketchbooks/3.-Preparation%20for%20the%20activity/2-Innovation%20services/>

My interactions

What activity am I exploring?

The following models correspond to the innovation services tasks, and also how the labs can approach their own activities. You can explore the identifying of where, why and who will interact or have a relationship in this activity.

Community Engagement

Lab to Lab Research

Business Engagement

Thoughts / Objectives

You can define the objective and thoughts through different perspectives:

- **individual:** my personal process of change
- **observer:** what dynamics promote change through the activity we are planning
- **transformer:** with my individual process and observation, can I evaluate, how the shemakes values are reflected?

A trip of empowerment and a way to connect with likeminded individuals which allow my vision to be stated clearly

- The intimacy that comes with working with a small group of participants
- The suspension of disbelief in order to speculate on gender futures

The activity aims at envisioning gender futures, raising awareness on gender biases and empowering self expression and personal vision

Figure 18. Marilena's example: "My interactions".

Activity

With which main actors of the Innovation system will I work?

- Academia Government **Society** Industry

What is my role as an ambassador in this process?
create foundations of a community and network for future collaborators

Which issues of gender inequality do I want to address?
the position of women in research and innovation

How can I create change through this activity?
introduce them current state of technologies and other female innovators

Which of the processes will I work on?

- Places** Design Make
- Territorial Wool Ecosystems | Local dyes for sustainable and productive territories | Small-scale tools for local production

What is my role as an ambassador in this process?
Wool ecosystem, Fabricademy program, DIY tools

What is the purpose of my research?
mapping other cultural environment and system

What kind of impact/interchange do I expect to have on the two community labs?
knowledge, experience and social exchange

Which of the business points will I work on?

- Start-up Lines **Collaboration**
- Ignition of ideas and new opportunities | products, collections, materials | exchange of knowledge, co-creation

What is my role as an ambassador in this process?
provide general information and let know use tools, develop a personal or group project

What kind of activity will I work on?
o SUSTENID

What kind of impact/interchange do I expect to have on the two community labs?
Icelandic handcraft / spanish innovation & technology

Figure 19. Petra's description of her activity

This allows the Ambassadors to have a detailed activity description under **“Activity”** (see Figure 19) for 1) a better understanding of what they’re going to do as activities and 2) a better feeling of the activities. They could then share this information and a clear plan to discuss internally in the labs.

Sketchbook Experience in the Transfer Lab¹²

This Sketchbook is about the Ambassador's experience in the Transfer Lab, tracking Ambassadors' capacity to emerge as leaders and 'carry the message' to their peers in other cultural and geographical contexts.

The Experience in the Transfer Lab Sketchbooks connects the dots from the previous sketchbooks and what they do in their travels. It explores the local ecosystem beforehand and gives an overview during and after the activity.

This Sketchbook is divided into five sections:

Arrival

First impressions of the city/culture, illustrating the experience with new factors such as language and resources describing the local ecosystem.

- The first impression of the new city.
- The results of exploring around the new city.

Figure 20. Andreas's sketchbook.

¹² More details on this Sketchbook can be found here: <http://fabricademy.fabcloud.io/shemakes/handbook/3.-role%20models%20and%20voices/Ambassadors/Sketchbooks/2-Experience%20in%20the%20transfer%20lab/>

Lab

The Ambassadors give their impression of the Transfer Lab, describing the place and the location, machines and setup compared to their experience in the partner lab in phase one. This item highlights how labs in every place have some things in common but are specific to the needs of each city or town Figure 18.

Figure 21. Tasnim's sketchbook with Transfer Lab Team.

Activity

Here, Ambassadors describe their experiences and interaction with the participant labs or lab leaders. Here WP4 encourages Ambassadors to reflect on:

- What activity did you do, and how did it go?
- Can you tell us about one exciting observation about an interaction with a participant?
- Positive feedback, like someone saying they would like to study this further.

The workshop description includes:

- Summary of what the activities were about and what was the role of the Ambassador.
- Who was the audience for the workshop?
- "Moments of success as a shemakes Ambassador"
- Describe what you have done during the activities.

Figure 22. Jessica's sketchbook.

Reflections and Takeaways

In this section, WP4 encourages Ambassadors to reflect about their goals, the values, and the impact through the shemakes' experience in the lab for the participants and how this role brings changes in their future careers.

Figure 23. Tasnim's Reflections on the experience in the Transfer Lab.

Porto on the 6th of April and went directly to her appointed lab, VIVA Lab. However, she was expecting the lab to be different. She found, to her surprise, similarities to the Fab Lab Leon. On her arrival, she felt welcome, and didn't have any difficulties with communication since she speaks Spanish, which is similar to Portuguese. The day before the workshop, she prepared stuff kits with the lab.

Activity: For the workshop session and as a part of her mission, Carla had to teach children aged 6 to 7 at a local school. The friendliness of the children, together with the familiar environment at the school, made her experience more fun and easier. Even though she was nervous at the workshop's beginning, the activity ended with an excellent result. The children were taught how to create e-monsters together; they were introduced to electronic textiles, and despite some difficulties, they were able to learn how to do it.

Figure 26. The children were taught how to make e-monsters.

Reflection: "Enjoy the experience and always be grateful for the unique opportunities you are brought to."

Takeaways: "Knowledge, culture, experience".

Table 11. Carla's experience outcomes.

Values

Equality: Equality was present during the whole activity.
Collaborative: They helped each other.
Welcoming differences: Even though she and the students were from different nationalities, she noted that it didn't make a difference. They were very respectful to her.

Empowering: She felt empowered because she took the main role at the workshop.

Inspiring: "I was able to encourage them, since they were capable of doing it."

During the workshop session, the young women were introduced to science through the workshop activities, where they gained technological knowledge.

Gender

"There weren't any differences there in Viva Lab when it came to gender inequality," according to her. "Both the girls and boys were able to carry out the activities that they were introduced to without difficulties or problems. They were very respectful to each other, too."

Network

She had the chance to create a network of girls and boys of the same age with different mindsets and was motivated to continue communicating with her peers and exchanging experiences and activities in their labs.

Lucía (LEON)

Figure 27. Athens, Greece.

Lucia, like Carla, was one of the youngest Ambassadors and a part of Nuria's group. She went to Greece to share her own vision of the curiosity path. She had the opportunity to tour and get to know Athens, where she experienced the traces of its old history in the streets. But she was most impressed by the Acropolis, the Temple of Olympian Zeus and the Plaka district.

After looking around, she went directly to their Transfer Lab. Although the lab wasn't as big as FabLab León like she was expecting, Decode Lab gave her all the necessary help in her journey.

Activity: For her workshop, she taught how to make e-monsters to children aged 6 to 14 from 2 different classes at a local museum, where they developed the activity

together. The children were very active and asked questions when they didn't understand something.

Figure 28. The E-monsters made by the children in Athens.

Reflections: At the beginning, Lucia faced some difficulties in instructing the children, but it got easier with time. She didn't find any difficulties in communication since their audience had a level of English higher than what she was expecting and used to in Spain. She felt at ease because of that. "Sometimes we don't value the moments until they become memories."

Takeaways: "Breathtaking opportunities, new experiences, networking"

Table 12. Lucia's experience outcomes.

Gender	She did not find any gender inequality since everyone worked together and helped each other without any problems.
Network	This experience allows meeting all kinds of people with different backgrounds, cultures, and mentalities, and that's what happened with Lucia. It was interesting for her that she met children her age from other countries. Not only, but her experience of teaching in the different environment of the museum made her experience unforgettable.

Tasnim Hussain (IAAC)

Figure 29. Tasnim in Berlin.

Tasnim was a part of the Discovery Path team led by Anastasia from IAAC, she travelled to Germany for her workshop. When she arrived in Berlin, she faced some challenges because of language and communication barriers, but she managed to enjoy herself.

“The amazing natural views and the modern stamp of the city caught me. It was very impressive to see the trains penetrating the mountains and green forests. Breathtaking views and sight feeding.”

As soon as she arrived, she went directly to the Textile Prototyping Lab of Berlin, which was an “impressive open-innovation space” for her .

Figure 30. Tasnim with Sigrid (Sigi), Essi and Kamil (the one behind the camera).

The lab is part of an important research institute, Fraunhofer IZM. “[...]Together with other labs in the institute, TPL serves a wide range of clients, including industrial projects, research-based projects, innovation projects and even individual entrepreneurship projects.” What makes TPL unique, in her opinion, was the space’s accessibility, which made co-working with other labs possible. There were also advanced machines in the institute.

Tasnim was particularly fond of the lab team, which was “amazingly” designed with multiskilled members from different specialities, including electronics engineering, textile and surface design, and materials engineering.

Activity: Tasnim had different activities during her journey:

- **E-Textiles Workshop:** With this workshop, Tasnim introduced the basics of e-textile materials and the TPL modular kit to make interesting interactive textile projects. The participants in this workshop were master students from two different institutes. They came to the workshop with little knowledge about e-textiles, but left with a clear understanding and a reasonable implementation plan. Even though she was not able to attend the first day of the workshop, she still got the chance to discuss ideas with students and mentor them during the second day.
- **Smart Stitches Workshop:** For this workshop, she made interactive swatches with the other participants using cross stitching as a traditional technique for embroidered pieces.

Figure 31. Tasnim's smart stitches workshop.

- **KHB Students' Presentations:** She attended some presentations of master students from KHB. During their presentations, they introduced different techniques for fibre making through spinning yarns, materials upcycling and

biomaterials, and different techniques of looming to make patterned fabric pieces. This was a very good chance for her to see the diversity and results of different experimental approaches to design interesting featured textiles.

Reflections: “Life is about the journey, not the destination. Pack lighter, travel further!”

Takeaways:

Figure 32. Tasnim’s takeaways.

Table 13. Tasnim’s experience outcomes.

Values

Through this experience, she learned many things:

- It is necessary to be open-minded and flexible to adapt to your new and unfamiliar environment.
- It is necessary to step out of our comfort zone and give a chance to experience new things
- The ripple effect¹³ is powerful and inspiring to make change. One small change can have an enormous impact.
- A keen learner is a good observer too. “When you are a good observer, you will be aware of the opportunities around you and will be surprised by the ones that you can create.”

Collaborative: Different entities, including universities, engaged in the activities.

Welcoming differences: The workshop was designed to be understandable for participants from different backgrounds; technical, artistic, and design.

Empowering: Tasnim noticed that it was necessary to be aware of the learning curve and not skip it. Most attendees felt empowered as they learned the basics of e-textiles which was confusing to them before the

¹³ **The ripple effect:** The spreading effect experienced as the result of a single event. .

workshop.

Inspiring: The discussions and showcase projects inspired most of the participants.

Gender

As time passed, the participants were less stressed and more comfortable during the workshop, since they learned how to deal with the newly presented technology.

She noticed that the gender-gap was still strongly present in the field: on one hand, there are still more women in the fashion field but with less knowledge in tech-fashion. And on the other, men dominate the technical/ engineering-related fields. This resulted in a prejudice that technology is “a difficult topic” to integrate into their products.

Network

Building up a network of researchers, innovators, sustainability advocates and designers.

Petra Garajová (IAAC)

Figure 33. Blönduós, Iceland.

Like Tasnim, Petra participated in the activities of the partner lab IAAC. She travelled to Iceland to conduct workshops at the Icelandic Textile Centre. After starting to work at the centre, Petra sympathised with the team and the atmosphere where she felt at home. She liked the teamwork of the lab members as well.

Activities: During the two weeks of her journey, Petra did multiple activities and participated in different workshops.

As a part of her workshops, she connected craftsmanship with:

- New technologies and materials
- Waste and biomaterials
- Biotechnology
- Digital manufacturing

Figure 34. Petra's biomaterials workshop at the Icelandic Textile Center.

She also made various **trips & visits** to different places:

- Sheep farm
- Design March - Talks Reykjavik
- Icelandic beach for the local materials
- BioPol laboratory in Skagatrönd

Figure 35. The sheep farm.

Her journey allowed her to have a knowledge exchange with other institutions and individuals, in her research path, during different events. 1) TC2 digital weaving loom 2) Wool spinning 3) Marine biotechnology science.

Reflections: Her journey to Iceland brought her many insights:

- **Learning-by-doing:** In order to adapt and learn something, you have to interact with the environment.
- **Community connections:** She established a nice collaboration and a long term friendship with the local lab manager.
- **Cultural heritage:** She experienced another culture and got in touch with the locals, which itself was a benefit for her.

Takeaways: The greatest learning was how to quickly respond and adapt to the audience you have in front of you and to find quick solutions to be able to overcome difficulties and problems.

She got to experience the local production up close and the resources and materials used by the international group she worked with.

Table 14. Petra's experience outcomes.

Values	From her journey, she learned a lot of new things and gained experience in teaching across various topics at the intersection of digital fabrication and biotechnology. This opportunity gave her the possibility of transferring knowledge between experts and communities. <i>Inspiring:</i> She helped the locals and showed them how to implement an innovation in the wool ecosystem. Not only that, she helped them by shifting handcraft techniques using new technologies. The added value from these workshops is learning how to build your own tools.
Gender	Being a textile research center, the audience is by default predominantly women. During the activities, there was higher participation of men in almost every activity - workshop of biomaterials, soft robotics or 3D modeling in particular.
Network	A network with a different mindset was built. Despite the local community being small, it has important international connections, since most of the attendees were from different international backgrounds.

Diane Wakim (ONLF)

Figure 36. Diane in Brussels.

As one of the two Ambassadors who were under the supervision of Team Cristina/Shannon and partner Lab Onl'fait, responsible for the Discovery Path Task, Diane travelled to the Green Fabric Lab in Brussels, Belgium.

On the Arrival: As suggested during the sessions and the Sketchbooks to prepare for the experience, Diana mentioned, "When I visit a new place, I always make a map in advance, with all the places I need or want to go to." She didn't lose time and visited different parts of the city. She "[...]saw an amazing exhibit at the Museum of Fine Arts, by Tanya Goel, who makes her own paints and pigments from construction sites waste." Afterwards, she went directly to the lab, where she "was happy to have such an opportunity to discover the Green Fabric Lab and to meet two of her role models in the field.[...] I had been following their projects for some time, and getting to be there and visit their amazing new place was great."

Activities:

- **Modular Fashion Workshop:** She did this workshop virtually with fourteen students from a design school. They learned how to create modular designs with Inkscape and produced them with laser cutters.

Figure 37. Modular fashion : paper prototyping, then assembling to create a garment.

- **Code+Textile Workshop:** This one was an In-lab workshop, where the participants were eight students from a design school who learned how to generate designs with code using TurtleStitch and then realise them with the embroidery machine.
- **Lab2Lab and exchange:** She participated in two days of lectures and workshops around Belgian wool production "Re-wool", where she experienced how wool is crafted. Her journey involved wool spinning, visiting a local tinctorial garden, machine knitting, etc. She also took the chance to present the shemakes project and the Fabricademy program to the participants.

Figure 38. Learning how to spin wool, and how to use the knitting machines.

Reflection: For her, having the chance to be in the Green Fabric Lab for an entire week during the workshop and during the Re:Wool Lab2Lab event was really appreciated. "[...] I was very happy with the workshops we did, especially the fact that the students really seemed to appreciate and get into it."

Takeaways: During her week in the Green Fabric Lab, she was very energised and motivated to do her work. Nothing was unfamiliar to her. They even shared a lot of common interests and developments, as well as several problems they both faced. It was thus a good chance to have an exchange of views as well as skills. By working together, especially with machines, she got more motivated to finish the projects that

she’s doing at the moment in Lyon. “It was nice to meet the community they created around their lab and get to know them better!”

Table 15. Diane’s experience outcomes.

<p>Values</p>	<p><i>Openness & collaborative:</i> Throughout the project, you got to learn to be more open and collaborative with others, and since being collaborative was one of the core values of the Green Fabric Lab, it made everything a lot easier. The students got to learn and to discover what they can do with open-source software too.</p> <p><i>Inspiring:</i> Her being an inspiring figure for the students was another gained value of this workshop. She taught them to understand how they can make use of the technology and gain ownership of the tool for their design process. They had an interesting discussion together about this topic.</p>
<p>Gender</p>	<p><i>Empowering:</i> At first, the girls were afraid to try something new and related to technology, but during the workshop, they overcame those fears. Diane had good feedback from some of the girls, especially regarding the fact that women teaching them technology made things less frightening.</p> <p><i>Still a hard topic:</i> She noticed that it’s still very hard to bring up the topic of gender with the students, since they don’t necessarily feel affected when it comes to that.</p>
<p>Network</p>	<p><i>Stronger links:</i> With this workshop, the link between Lyon labs and Brussel labs got stronger, which made it easier to communicate and to share knowledge with each other.</p> <p><i>Creating new links:</i> “I met a lot of amazing people to keep in contact with, during the week and also during the Re:wool event”</p>

Andrea Wolf-Simone (ONLF)

Alongside Diana, Andrea was part of the Discovery Path team that was led by Cristina and Shannon. When she arrived in the small old town of Vilnius in Lithuania, she was welcomed to two workspaces: The Vilnius Art Academy and Vivistop Lab.

With a 15 minute walk from the Vilnius Art Academy, the Vivistop Lab is easily accessible. The Lab was surrounded by a forest on one side and traditional houses on the other. “Big windows let the sunshine inside the lab, which creates a great feeling.”

Figure 39. The lab location.

Activities: On her first day at the lab, the participants came already motivated for her e-hero workshop. This activity contained two parts:

- First, they used modular design to create bags and small carpets.
- The second part introduced a simple electronic circuit to create the e-hero character.

For the next three days, she did different activities with the participants, who were mainly textile and fashion design students. (There were two boys among the participants.) The Fashion and Textile design department hosted her Shibori Experiment Workshop.

- **Day 1:** She introduced the Shibori Experiment Workshop and made an overview of the trending new field, "Digital tactility".
"Shibori Experiment Workshop is the best resource available to anyone from non-engineering backgrounds with electronics. The program shows an introduction to smart textiles and interaction design. It's a combination of traditional techniques and aesthetics (such as hand embroidery and Shibori) by infusing them with new materials and technologies (such as thermochromic pigment and conductive threads)."

Figure 40. Introduction to Shibori Experiment Workshop and overview into the new trend field "Digital tactility".

- **Day 2:** She showed them French haute couture moulage and draping techniques and then made some creative exercises with them

Figure 41. The French haute couture moulage and draping techniques workshop.

Afterwards, the students were asked to create a collage/mood board with their reflexions as a part of the daily evaluation.

Figure 42. The collage/mood-board.

- Day 3:** The third day of the journey, the students created their own embroidery with conductive threads, hand dyeing fabrics inspired by the Shibori technique. Then, they visually tested their own designs with a power supply.

Figure 43. "Create your own shibori".

Reflections: What made her Ambassador experience meaningful was what the participants gained from the workshop: new technical skills that were meant to be exclusive to men. They learnt how to infuse those with textile and handicraft skills which are the “social and cultural DNA of women”, by using a conductive thread, thermo-chromic pigment and a power supply.

This experience made it clear that in the future we will have a professional sector that will integrate traditional and innovative technologies.

Table 16. Andrea’s experience outcomes.

<p>Values</p>	<p><i>Equal:</i> She made sure to have all the participants do a daily evaluation through a collage / moodboard with some reflections about women’s equality in T+C education and work.</p> <p><i>Collaborative:</i> Participants (fashion and textile department) shared and worked with each other. They were from different backgrounds (fashion design, textile design and arts), which made the collaboration beneficial for all.</p> <p><i>Welcoming differences:</i> She made use of the different opinions that everyone has. She had daily evaluations and discussions in plenary about how to encourage women and girls to contribute independently of their background.</p> <p><i>Empowering:</i> Sharing some traditional and technological skills helped to “create a more comfortable entry point for tech explorations by women.”</p> <p><i>Inspiring:</i> Andrea, with the new skills she introduced to her workshop participants, was an inspirational figure to them: a woman working at the intersection of textiles, handicraft and technology and breaking stereotypes that technology is only made by men.</p>
<p>Gender</p>	<p>They approached gender through collaboration with each other.</p>

Alexandra Florea (REDU)

Alexandra arrived in Prato, Italy, on the 15th of May. She was part of the Community Engagement team under the mentorship of Andreea and Elvys from REDU. She was assigned to Lottozero Textile Laboratories, where she carried out different activities. Alexandra presented shemakes in different digital and hybrid venues, such as “STEM Out of the Box: Women Imagining New Career Paths Beyond Hard Science”. At the International Day of Women and Girls in Science 2022, she participated in the TCBL conference representing and giving insights into their vision of business engagement and giving some recommendations on how to encourage women to lose the fear of being an entrepreneur.

Figure 44. The Lottozero textile laboratories.

Activities: As a part of the business engagement workshop, her workshop involved showing and teaching the participants how to start a fashion business on the one hand and to create a new business line at a mixer event on the other.

Figure 45. Shemakes Mixer Event and Lab 2 Lab.

Figure 46. Alexandra's workshop on how to start a fashion business.

Reflections: During her workshop, Alexandra talked with participants about different topics related to textiles:

- Fashion & textile pollution
- Supply chains
- Funding female-led female businesses
- Cross-industry collaboration
- Skills development
- Inspiration: Textile Museum, Rifo Lab, Beste, Designers, Green Factory, ID-Eight
- Promoting sustainable textiles and business models

Takeaways: From this workshop, she concluded that to solve some of the problems related to textiles:

- Networking is key
- Support female entrepreneurs
- Combat fashion pollution
- Bond and connect strength

Table 17. Alexandra's experience outcomes.

Values	Openness and collaborative: Since she worked closely with different people in the workshop, she learnt how to be more open and collaborative. Inspirational: She became an inspiring figure for the women there.
Gender	Gender inequality in financing projects: Funding females, in general, is still an issue, let alone females in the textile business. However, partnerships can increase chances of accessing funding programs where supply chains are led by males.
Network	The birth of a future textile network where mixer events are valuable. Embed circular / life cycle thinking and sustainability topics in co-creation sessions.

Marilena Georgantzi (REDU)

Marilena was mentored by Andreea and Elvys from the partner Lab REDU. And, like Alexandra, she travelled to another country for her workshop. She went to London, in the UK. Marilena also participated in the activities in Florence. Her Input and disposition to contribute to the shemakes community and her interest in continuing to work with different Transfer Labs make Marilena an important addition for further opportunities in the Textiles and Fab lab Environment.

Figure 47. One of Marilena's photos of her travel to London.

Her assigned lab, the Centre for Circular Design, is situated along with other labs and studios at the University of the Arts London in Chelsea. She noted they were all enthusiastic with ideas, energy and creativity, and the team she worked with was "super creative". The activities carried out, jointly designed with shemakes and CCD, were hosted in the centre's main space. "A beautiful sunny space with big windows overlooking the street where swatches, samples, artefacts and other workshop results are spread around."

She got to work closely with Sanne Visser, who represented the Transfer Lab and is now part of the second round of the Ambassadors. Marilena shared that it was "inspiring and great getting to know her and her research!"

Activity: She led a Gender Futures workshop and assisted in the Gender Vision workshop. Gender Futures was a three-hour speculative design research workshop on gender and its manifestation through apparel, and is done by applying the principles of world-building and introducing participants to the methodologies of speculative design, "what if" scenarios and the concept of atmospheres and coherence when building a proposal. The workshop introduced the participants - textile graduate students - to the methodology of world-building. This was accomplished through examples from sci-fi literature and cinema, where their specific worlds were analysed. Modes of clothing and how the principles of the world structure were depicted were of key importance. For the last part of the workshop, participants were encouraged to define "what if" conditions that would differ from the current moment in the Anthropocene and use pre-designed worksheets to explore their ideas for apparel of the future while introducing themselves to the concepts of storyboards and affordances.

Figure 48. The pre-designed worksheets for the Gender Futures workshop.

Her workshop activities led to interesting observations and questions on:

- How shifting preconceptions on gender would alter society, industry and consumption standards.
- How clothing reflects gender and vice versa.
- How clothes can expose us or keep us safe.
- What is the connection between what we wear, who we are and the environment we inhabit.

Figure 49. Marilena's Gender Futures workshop.

Takeaways: From her side, her takeaways were on different levels:

- As an individual: The personal process of change.
- As an observer: What are the dynamics that promote change through the planned activity?
- As a transformer: With her individual process and observation, “the way that she makes values are reflected”

Table 18. Marilena’s experience outcomes.

<p>Values</p>	<p><i>Empowering:</i> The workshop raises awareness of gender biases and empowers self-expression and personal vision; it empowers women to express their visions and open up the discussion to the system of clothing.</p> <p><i>Equal:</i> All activities valued everyone’s voice equally, centred on the participation of women and nonbinary people.</p> <p><i>Welcoming differences:</i> Participants were from different parts of the world sharing different views of gender.</p> <p><i>Inspiring:</i> The workshop offered participants the opportunity to envision the world where gender is a spectrum, bodies feel safe, femininities are empowered, people own their bodies and create space for alternative ways of being.</p>
<p>Gender</p>	<p>The workshop was on gender and its manifestation through apparel, and it was done by applying the principles of world-building and by introducing participants to the methodologies of speculative design, “what if” scenarios and the concept of coherence when building a proposal.</p> <p>“It helped me focus on the gendered reality of a female designer. It allowed her to meet exciting, really female designers, students, and entrepreneurs.”</p>
<p>Network</p>	<p>Marilena is the administrator of the Piraeus Makerspace, part of the Pop Machina Horizon 2020 project focused on making and circular economies.</p>

Jessica Stanley (WAAG)

Figure 50. Ljubljana, Slovenia.

Jessica was part of the Waag Ambassadors and she received guidance from Cecilia and Beatriz, the leaders of Task 2.3 innovation Path. She travelled to Ljubljana in Slovenia. As a PhD Candidate at Nottingham Trent University, Department of Engineering, UK, Jessica contributed with her experience in a research environment and could also benefit from the exchange and gain confidence in her work at the lab. Having different reflections and sharing them during the event in Florence. Jessica also participated in different interviews. Her voice will inspire many young and future generations interested in e-textiles and wearable technology.

Arrival: For Jessica, the place was new and since she arrived on the weekend; she had more time to explore. "It's a small city with lots of interesting architecture, and the people are very welcoming." Then, she went to RogLab where she was impressed by the team working behind the scenes there; she said that they were good at what they were doing. "RogLab in its current form, is a small but interesting space, and it was fun for me to be back in the open environment of a FabLab."

Activity: She made two different trips with different activities, topics, and participants:

- **Trip 1:** Community Engagement. Her two activities involved the FabLab community. She participated in a focus group on the gender equality plan for the new Rog Center opening in 2023. She also designed & facilitated an e-textiles workshop with the RogLab team.

Figure 51. The finished quilt (left) and Lucija's shemakes LED module (right).

- **Trip 2:** Discovery path. Jessica participated in the Biomaterials workshops with university students from different backgrounds, including Slovenia & nearby countries, where she supported them in planning and observation.

Figure 52. Casting bioplastic on a t-shirt during Lucrezia Strano's workshop.

Figure 53. Laser cutting earrings from apple bioplastics during Uroš Novak's workshop.

Reflections: Working with RogLab enriched her experience in terms of knowledge exchange with “like-minded people”, more than bringing her skill, or the shemakes values in her role as an Ambassador. In this, she *succeeded in supporting the work they were doing during her journey.*

Takeaways: “One of the things I valued most about being a Fabricademy student was the atmosphere of curiosity and encouragement, and it was great to see that replicated in shemakes activities.”

Table 19. Jessica’s experience outcomes.

<p>Values</p>	<p><i>Equal:</i> All activities valued everyone’s voice equally, centred on the participation of women and nonbinary people.</p> <p><i>Collaborative:</i> All the activities involved people working together, whether creating a gender equality plan or making e-textiles or biomaterials.</p> <p><i>Welcoming differences:</i> The hands-on workshops allowed participants to explore their own interests and to try different approaches.</p> <p><i>Empowering:</i> The hands-on activities empowered participants with skills, but also brought them together in a supportive environment where they were shown positive female (and sometimes male) role models.</p> <p><i>Inspiring:</i> The activities showed the potential of e-textiles and biomaterials, in the hope of inspiring the younger designers and makers to search alone and to find out more about these areas-</p>
<p>Gender</p>	<p>The gender equality focus group specifically discussed the different experiences of people from different backgrounds, and how to create an inclusive Fab Lab environment for all people.</p>
<p>Network</p>	<p>As a former Fabricademy student (2018/2019) Jessica brought the Fabricademy network to the shemakes project.</p>

Irene Caretti (WAAG)

Irene intended to participate as an Ambassador working in the Lab to Lab research in the Farmlab in Austria for her workshop. However, at that time the Lab members had Covid and due to parental leave, she couldn’t carry out the activity in the estimated period from M13 to M18. However, Irene participated in several activities for the preparation meeting. She was very motivated during the program and the experience helped her to reflect on her career path and to open up new possibilities in the project. Furthermore, she participated in the sessions and feedback and in the consortium meeting in Florence.

Camille Le Gal (MAKE)

Camille was mentored by Victor of makesense, responsible for the Business Engagement task. She travelled to Lyon in France to carry out two different activities at Le textile Lab. She was very enthusiastic on her first day, after visiting two different “Textile Lab” locations, one in Oullins and the other in Lyon, with Paulina the lab coordinator. Camille is one of the youngest and more active entrepreneurs among the Ambassadors, which however means that the lab environment is not familiar to her. She collaborated with the Transfer Lab, giving advice to different women entrepreneurs in the earlier stages of pitching ideas. She was impressed with the impact of the lab and how the space mobilises women makers and entrepreneurs and empowers them to stay strong and further develop their ideas.

Figure 54. Le Textile Lab.

Activity: As part of the Business Engagement activities, Camille had different workshops, participants, and topics, but all involving innovation in business and the creation of a culture of entrepreneurial skills:

- **Codev shemakes with 5 entrepreneurs** or women starting with 1 idea

Figure 55. A group meeting.

- **One to One meetings :**
 - Manon founder – Palympe
 - Souad founder – Illya, a women's & modest sportswear brand
 - Tim & Thibault: Feat.coop, a Social startup and a platform to identify textile waste stocks.

Figure 56. One to One meeting session.

- **Conference with Camille** on “How do you go from a large Luxury Group to a Startup with Impact?”

Reflection: “No matter the maturity of your project, you can be inspired by ANYONE and you can give to ANYONE. Sharing is always a **benefit.**”

#SharingIdeas

#OutsideMyBox

Takeaways: She felt energised after her meetings. Her day was full of surprises, and she came to the realisation that no matter your age, you still can pursue your dreams. She was especially fascinated by entrepreneurs that started their businesses from scratch at the age of 50. They had a special entrepreneurial flame that gave them a push forward to do what they wanted. She also discovered a new sector called “humble fashion”, or modest fashion.

Table 20. Camille’s experience outcomes.

Values	The values here were on a personal level: “be open-minded” “be brave, always fight and never give up” “Because the road is long and not easy”
Gender	Through her journey she gained a new vision on the women’s & modest sportswear products.
Network	Network introductions Business & sales advices

Melanie (MAKE)

Melanie participated in the first phase of OnL’Fait activities and started later as a substitute for one Ambassador. Melanie thus became the makesense Ambassador for Business Engagement, but in parallel, she did activities in the Discovery Path, which was a difficult situation of matching. Melanie was assigned to the Ziphouse Design Hub in Chişinău, Moldova, but for safety reasons in travelling to Moldova, while affected by the war in Ukraine, the plan changed. Melanie, as an active student at HEAD, offered her support online. In the end, due to these complications in addition to her need to study, the activities could not be completed as planned.

4.4. Feedback

We invited Ambassadors to reflect on their experiences and understand their ideas and their wishes for the future: “How to develop in the future with the shemakes community.”

With this purpose, WP4 developed an interview session in which to discuss their feedback and ideas during the experience. As tools for the structure of the meeting, a form and a co-creation board summarised their wishes and further ideas to develop as a shemakes community.

The feedback form

This format helped to formulate the interview questions, while giving the Ambassadors time to reflect and complete their answers.

The form has four sections:

1. The personal experience with shemakes
2. The activities
3. Sketchbooks
4. Social media

The personal experience with shemakes

The first part describes what kind of impact the shemakes experience had on their personal and professional levels. Overall, the experience had a good influence in their lives.

For the 1st question in this category, 5 out of 7 answered that they “believe that the shemakes Ambassador has enhanced their practice to be a woman innovator in the textile and fashion industry.” The figure below shows how they described this.

Figure 57. “How did the shemakes Ambassador enhance your practice to be a woman innovator in the textile and fashion industry?”

The activities

Here the questions were about the different activities the Ambassadors did with the Gurus and the Transfer Labs during their biweekly sessions, the gift weave challenge, and the one-on-one sessions, and their opinions about these activities. Most of the Ambassadors found them to be useful. For the question “What did you like about the

(biweekly sessions, gift weave challenge, the one-on-one sessions) meetings?”, 4 out of 7 answered as shown below.

Figure 58. The answers to the question concerning the activities.

Sketchbooks

Here they were asked about the tools that had been used and their opinions about them. They mostly were happy with the sketchbooks, though using Mural was confusing for all of them. They found that the workshop for planning the Sketchbook and the experience in the Transfer Lab with the Sketchbooks were the most useful. Their reasons were as follows:

Figure 59. Opinions on the Sketchbooks.

Social media

This final section aimed to know if the Ambassadors were planning to share their work via social media. Only 2 of 7 answered, positively, as shown below:

Figure 60. Reasons for using social media.

Ambassadors' co-creation feedback

A co-creative feedback session asked Ambassadors how they would identify with a badge, how they would inspire their peers, and what they had gained through their work with the Transfer Labs and overall as a part of the shemakes network. The figure below shows selected badges for the Ambassador role: maker, listener, collaborator, courageous and empowering others, to feel supported.

Figure 61. Ambassador badges.

We then discussed possibilities for improvement, asking the Ambassadors what they liked and what they wished was different about their experience, as well as their recommendations to the next round of Ambassadors. The following table summarises the main points.

Table 21. Ambassadors' Feedback session

Likes

- "Chance to connect with other labs and what they are doing"
- "It was very special to be able to travel to share your thoughts and exchange points of view."
- "Work for it until the end"
- "Make and solve by yourself"
- "I had a great experience meeting a new culture and new people."
- "Fake it until you make it"
- "In the middle of nowhere, international happiness, open mind"
- "Make Exchange and learn cross-cultural experiences from the beginning."
- "I thought it was wonderful to meet new people."
- "It made me happy being able to communicate with everyone and successfully overcome it."
- "Share ideas, link with researchers"
- "Collaboration with the Transfer Labs"
- "I learned not to be afraid of speaking in public."

Wishes

- "Be for both workshops. The logistics in the short time (more time to organise the workshops)."
- "To visit other labs"
- "Chance to keep going and have feedback from other people face to face and online"
- "I wish I could take part in more activities like the Wool Mondays in person."
- "Keep Ambassadors interactive or project assign from the Transfer Lab"
- "It would be more effective to be active after the trip is finished."
- "Doing something during the time"
- "The organisation and promotion of the works"
- "Communication / interaction with locals as most of the participants were international."

Wonders

- "Feedback from other Ambassadors"
- "Communication on the activities"
- "I wonder how we will keep in touch."
- "Learn from content from someone else or from other communities."

Advice to future Ambassadors

- "Cooperation with other Ambassadors or labs"
- "Contribute but explore things you don't know."
- "Meeting with others: labs and Ambassadors."
- "Exchange of skill and knowledge with the Transfer Lab"
- "Visit labs."
- "Go and meet people in person."
- "Having one goal to build something together"
- "Activity or project together"

4.5. Second round Ambassadors

To expand the network and develop the shemakes community, a second call for Ambassadors was planned towards the end of the project. 18 additional Ambassadors from the partner and Transfer Labs were appointed in this phase. As the shemakes project officially ends in December 2022, this second call aimed to ensure that the values promoted and activities created during the project can continue over time by engaging the new ambassadors with the community through:

- **Support organisation:** in shemakes meet-ups and iteration sessions reflecting the Ambassador's and the community's role in supporting the Transfer Lab's vision and promoting the shemakes values.
- **Promote and share:** Be able to explain what we do and promote it to others in a general sense; contribute their own perspective and content or activities to the project.

- **Collaborate and connect:** With their expertise; 1) Sharing stories and learnings, Opportunities for Internal or external Coaching / Mentoring, 2) The possibility to connect with the Ambassadors and, in general, the shemakes community.

Selection

In M18, the process for the second round of Ambassadors started, with a second call for Ambassadors followed by evaluation, selection, and communication of results. The following is the timeline for these steps.

- August 1st, 2022: Start the selection process
- August 30th, 2022: Final Decision Scoring
- August 30th, 2020: Evaluation second call closed.
- September 8th, 2022: Announcement of new Ambassadors
- End September: Start of Ambassador activities

Unlike the public call in the first phase, for the second call new candidates were nominated by labs, together with 1st round Ambassadors and reference labs, amongst past participants of shemakes activities with the following criteria:

- To have participated in at least one shemakes activity or been an active member of a shemakes lab.
- Be in contact with the local lab and community.
- Be willing to promote the shemakes values.
- Be able to communicate in English and in their native language.

In the case of minors: parents' signature for ethics and data consent for any activities, including participation in the networking sessions that may be recorded. The information and requirements were slightly changed from the first selection process and were sent to the nominees by email and in a short questionnaire, which was the base of the scoring.

Nomination

Each lab nominated 1-3 persons from the SU activities who were particularly involved in the further expansion of the lab and shemakes community engagement, for a total of 30 nominees. The nominees were informed about their recommendation by email and asked to fill out a questionnaire to facilitate the selection process.

Evaluation

The questionnaires, based on the first selection form, had a few questions to make the process easy for everyone while taking into account their experience with the activities in which they had previously participated and their interest and

commitment as future Ambassadors. The evaluation process was primarily conducted through contact with the laboratories. MATRIX provided an Excel spreadsheet with the parameters listed below. Examples were provided to allow comparative scoring, and the Gurus collaborated in adjusting these criteria. The following items defined the scoring:

- Shemakes activity/ community and network
 - Have you participated in a shemakes activity?
 - Have you had a chance to work with or meet a shemakes “Guru”?
 - *resonance of shemakes in their own network
- Expertise
 - Have you participated in any relevant laboratories or workshops, or have any specific training that might be relevant to your role as an Ambassador?
 - Online presence: If you have some places online where we can see more about your activities and projects, please share them here.
- Shemakes values enablers
 - What did you learn in these activities, and why do you think it was essential to your growth as a person?
 - *support and promote the shemakes values growing together, enabling a continuation of shemakes community.
- Mission Driven
 - Why do you think you would be a good shemakes Ambassador?
 - What can you offer to others, but also what can you gain or how will this opportunity help you?

Table 22. Criteria weighting.

Criteria	Weighting
shemakes activity / community and network	25%
Expertise	25%
Shemakes value Enablers	25%
Mission Driven	25%
TOTAL	100%

Quantitative evaluation

For the second selection round, 18 Labs nominated 30 Candidates from their environment, from which 18 new Ambassadors were selected.

The majority (78%) of nominees were age 25 and over (Innovation Path), followed by 19% between 8 and 18 (Curiosity Path) and 3% 18-25 (Discovery Path).

Figure 62. Age of the nominees.

7% of the second round nominees were males, 3% were non-binary, and the rest were female nominees.

Figure 63. Gender of nominees.

Out of the 30 candidates, only 13% joined the e-monsters shemakes activity. Some of the candidates (7%) attended the Co-development sessions, while 27% attended either the REWOOL activity (13%) or the Bacteria and Fungi for Textiles activity (7%) or the sanded workshops (7%). And the remaining 45% they either participated in other various shemakes activities(43%) or didn't share details (2%).

Figure 64. Activities.

Regarding the labs, most of the nominees were from the Leon, Textile and Viva laboratories (36%). The TP, Decode and Center Rog laboratories account each for 6%, while the remainder were from 12 other labs.

Figure 65. Labs used by the nominees.

The majority (91%) of the nominees were from Europe and more precisely from the following countries: France, Spain, Slovenia, Greece, or the Republic of Moldova. From these, most of the nominees were originally (17%) from France. A minor percentage of 3% each was from Italy, Lithuania, Austria, Iceland, the Netherlands, Germany, Switzerland, and Romania. The remaining 9% of applicants came from other non-EU countries.

Figure 66. Nominee countries of origin.

The most popular social media platform used by participants is Instagram (36%). Most of the nominees use other types of platforms, like personal sites. As a professional network and to make social contacts, 29% of applicants use LinkedIn.

Figure 67. Social media channels used by the nominees.

Qualitative evaluation:

All 18 labs reviewed the applications. During the open discussion, the labs presented their candidate and gave qualitative feedback, and the 18 candidates with the highest scores were selected.

A crucial point was their motivation to be an Ambassador and the experience and expertise they had gained during the workshops and in their contact with the labs. The main goal of the Ambassadors is to convey the spirit of shemakes activities and represent a group of future innovators some testimonies are pictured in the following questions:

Why do you think you would be a good shemakes Ambassador?

Here we have the answers where they described their *personal experience* in the shemakes activities.

Figure 68. Ambassador applicants' experiences during the shemakes activities.

Have you participated in any relevant laboratories or workshops, or do you have any specific training that might be relevant to your role as an Ambassador?

Here are some answers that show the *mission driven* of the selected Ambassadors

Figure 69. Ambassador applicants: Mission-driven.

Results

From the 30 nominees, 18 Ambassadors from 18 Labs were chosen, In a joint meeting and accepted by all Labs meeting. A roundtable of the chosen ones was held where all gurus and transfer leaders agreed on the process. There was an opportunity to include male participation and diversity in the distribution of labs. Another chance was given to select peers to support each other in the future process: e.g. two men, two PhDs students and two girls from the learning pathways of curiosity. The following table lists the selected 18 Ambassadors with their respective Partner lab.

Table 25 : List of the second round of ambassadors

Name	Expertise	SU activity	Reference Lab	Country
Adina Orboi	bio-based materials	Works for a sustainable company	REDU	Romania
Adrian Torres	Electrical Rail substations. and media community manager Fab Foundation	12F International Day of Women and Girls in Science.	Fab Lab León	Spain
Blanca	Student	"Minifabricademy for girls" & "E-Monster"	Fab Lab León	Spain
Capucine Robert	Product designer	e-textile workshop	Le textile lab (Lyon)	France
Chloé Manon Piaud	Fashion designer	Wool mondays day 1 and 3	FabLab Onl'fait	Switzerland
Christina Antzoulatou	Architect	e-monster in the museum	Decode Fab Lab	Greece
Jooyoung Park	UX researcher and designer Human-Computer Interaction Design CHI 2022	Workshop: Actuated Materials and Soft Robotics Strategies	MATRIX Interaction Design Team / KTH Royal Institute of Technology	South Korea
Lucija Jankovec	Creative artist	Discovery path, Community Engagement	Center Rog	Slovenia

Name	Expertise	SU activity	Reference Lab	Country
Marjana Raspor	Designer	Innovative Cellulosic and Biomaterials	Center Rog	Slovenia
Martin Gutmann	3D Print Technician Lab Manager	Innovation Path, Lab to Lab	FarmLab	Austria
Maurane Montreau	Mentor for sustainable business	Mentorship program shemakes	makesense	France
Olivia Kotsifa	Freelance designer Founder of SYN Fab Lab, architect	E-monster at the museum, Digitalising looms, e-SDG's, Digital Textile recycling	Decode	Greece
Rita Perdiço	Student	I sanded my t-shirt, I sanded my tote bag, e-slippers, world café gender bridging, visit to Covilhã	VIVALab	Portugal
Sanne Visser	Designer, maker, researcher	CCD shemakes Gender Futures Workshop,	Centre for Circular Design	Netherlands
Sara Diaz Rodriguez	Founder of Studio HILO	Spinning Workshop	TPL	Spain
Silvia Piantini	Designer	Lottozero survey Designer Directory	Lottozero	Italy
Stéphanie Vilaphiou	Designer	Lab to Lab Rethinking Wool + Discovery Path	Green Fabric	France
Caroline Tugara	Director Executive	shemakes Fashion Brunch	ZIPHOUSE Fashion Innovation Hub	Republic of Moldova

At the following link you will find the information published on the website [Network | shemakes](#) in detail.

Second round Ambassadors' activities

Once the project is completed, all 30 Ambassadors, including the 18 selected in the second round, will actively ensure that the values promoted and activities created during the project will continue and expand over time. The goal of second round Ambassador's activities in the final months of the project aimed to prepare them for that role and align them to the 12 first round Ambassador, allowing them to: 1) Create a space for sharing and understanding the shemakes' mission to create equality and collaboration and to actively empower and inspire women. And 2) Contribute to establishing close relationships at the Ambassador level.

WP4 developed tools to support these objectives by navigating the network and the materials developed in the project, allowing the second round Ambassadors to fully participate in an active exchange and expansion of the shemakes network. Similar to the first Ambassadors round, we created a timeline of activities until the end of the project:

- 5th of October 2022: Q&A and introduction session
- 4th of November 2022: Gender Vision Workshop
- 5th of December 2022: Give weave challenge
- 3rd to 30th November 2022: Opportunities in TCBL and Fabricademy
- 30th of November 2022: TCBL Conference

Vision workshop

As with the first round, the second round Ambassadors were invited to an online workshop where they were introduced to the shemakes vision.

Figure 70. Gender Vision workshop second round Ambassadors online.

Storytelling: Here, the Ambassadors did a collective storytelling that was led by Kerstin Junge from Tavistock Institute using online co-creation tools. This activity

aimed to create conversation despite differences in background and age and to provide space for story-making as powerful tools for connection.

The participants were divided into two groups where each in turn would add one sentence to the previous contributions to make a single, collective story. The facilitator began the story with the phrase, 'Once upon a time, there was a group of women who wanted to change the world of textiles...'

The following is the story from one of the groups: *"...So, they started the group of shemakes and to form a network together"... "to stay connected they started to build a digital community"... "and they involved a man in their community, and the men were also very surprised about how interesting the work of textiles is, and be engaged in the community"... "through this they create an object that represents their values, they present this to the public and inspire them."*

The goal was to help the Ambassadors to work spontaneously without previous plans, to strengthen their collaborative ability with each other, and to promote their self-expression.

Reflections: The new Ambassadors shared many thoughts afterwards concerning their perceptions about gender.

- Martin, (*Lab to lab research*) an Ambassador from Farm lab, shared one of his social experiences. He grew up in the countryside, where (like anywhere else in Europe) jobs are mostly categorised per gender, and he wants to change such perspectives and mindsets. There are no gender barriers that can prevent women and men from doing what they like. His experience in France was a turning point for him. He said: "There, gender didn't make much difference, e.g. women did industrial chimney constructions, and that was socially accepted." For that, he wants to break these gender stereotypes and do something that has always been linked to women, which is textiles. Being an Ambassador would allow him to do that.
- Olivia, (*Community engagement path*) also shared that she wants "to spread the word" that women are, like men, able to do anything.
- Rita, (*Curiosity path*) hoped that this would give her a good chance to talk with young girls like herself, who may have no one around them to discuss such topics with, and to make them understand what gender vision is all about.

Gift weave challenge

The gift weave challenge shares the same mission of bringing a contribution to the shemakes network. This activity focuses on 1) tools of communication and sharing voices, especially while preparing presentations or content during the opportunities

activities and 2) to enable Ambassadors through this format to make connections within the group.

For them, it was interesting to get to know each other this closely and to know what kind of expertise and “gift”, meaning contribution, each one could bring to the community. But most importantly, it was a chance to reflect on themselves. “I think it is always good to reflect on your own negative traits or the things that you’re not good at. And reflecting on which situation might be useful.” “You need to think more around you” (Sanne, CCD Ambassador). Most importantly, the idea for this exercise is to connect with each other, with other Ambassadors and with labs for future collaborations.

Figure 71. Adina and Sanne during the gift weave challenge.

Closing the session, they discussed the importance of sharing experiences and listening to interesting discussions, as happened during the TCBL Conference or the International Day of Women and Girls in Science. These events are considered to be a good opportunity to shape collaboration with peers, where different people from different labs and places can connect. At this conference, some of the Ambassadors from the first and second rounds got the chance to meet, which allowed to get in touch and enable further possibilities for collaboration.

Adina, for instance, shared that she is still in contact with one of the first round Ambassadors, Alexandra, who has started her own sustainability company. She's also going to collaborate as an artist on a project on occasion of the Romanian Creative Week, collaborating with partner lab REDU.

Opportunities

This includes activities planned to facilitate relationships with local stakeholders (institutions, researchers, companies, citizens, etc.) and to take advantage of any opportunities to expand the community beyond its current scope. Thus, WP4 focused on promoting and encouraging Ambassadors to showcase their work by offering

opportunities for visibility in the existing TCBL and Fabricademy ecosystems and communicating future opportunities in conjunction with the labs. In this way, WP4 aims to support exchange and the growth of the network. Two examples are the TCBL Jam Sessions and the Fabricademy Inspirational session.

At one of the TCBL Jam Sessions, Capucine Robert presented her new entrepreneurial project Nalba, a slow initiative creating wool rugs. This collection is shaded with plants and inspired by regional forms to weave emotions into textile objects. Taking a bioregional approach, Capucine Robert and her partner Lavinia Ghimbasan believe it is possible to design on-ground by emerging themselves into and being inspired by local contexts: in this case, the Transylvanian region of Romania."

Figure 72. TCBL Jam Sessions: Capucine Robert presenting Nalba.

At a Fabricademy Inspirational session, Ambassador Joo Young Park introduced her PhD research project about applications and implications of soft robotics, as an inspiration and impulse for the Fabricademy alumni. The presentation was titled "Synergetic Collaboration between Intimate Touch and Soft Robotics: Opportunities and Challenges"¹⁴. Jooyoung, as a feminist interaction designer, talked about how she approaches soft robotics technologies in the context of intimate care. She also highlighted critical thinking in designing intimate technologies drawing from the ongoing work in her research group¹⁵ that investigates the dynamic relationships between subjects and objects of touching through the lens of intimacy and how soft robotic technologies can be leveraged to yield a diverse spectrum of bodily knowledge. She presented different opportunities and challenges in exploring close individual bodily Touch using Soft Robotics technologies, as is shown below.

¹⁴ Workshop Position Paper: Actuated Materials and Soft Robotics Strategies for Human Computer Interaction Design Computer Human Interaction Conference, CHI22

¹⁵ Critical Feminist Computing Group: Part of this group is researching and developing Interaction Design Knowledge and Materials with the focus on how technology could and might intimately touch our bodies. At KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Division of Media Technology and Interaction Design, School of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science supervised by Prof. Madeline Balaam and Prof. Marianela Ciolfi Felice

Figure 73. Fabricademy session Joo Young Park presenting “Synergetic Collaboration between Intimate Touch and Soft Robotics: Opportunities and Challenges”.¹⁶

4.6. Gurus and Ambassadors at the shemakes Conference¹⁷

The shemakes conference was the closing event of the project. The event was jointly organised with TCBL in the context of “TCBL Days”, a series of hybrid events throughout November of each year that highlight issues in ongoing projects of which TCBL is a partner. The shemakes event, titled “Welcoming Differences”, presented the main project results and opened the debate on how an “ecosystem of opportunities” can bridge the current gender and innovation gap in the textile and clothing industry. Throughout the conference, shemakes’ activities related to STEM skills, entrepreneurial skills, community building and the wool lab model were discussed.

WP4 contributed to the event by collecting the voices of the role models, namely from the Ambassadors, Gurus, and Advisors and shemakes members from the first and second phases, and exploring the impact of their experiences in their leadership roles in their activities. Below is a summary of the shemakes voices of Gurus, Ambassadors and Transfer Labs leaders.

Figure 74. “Welcoming Differences” conference during the TCBL days.

¹⁶Presentation can be found in the following link <https://vimeo.com/778940374/94866acbf3>

¹⁷ Welcoming Differences: the shemakes final conference. More information can be found under the following link : <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yjnUPoIAOew&feature=youtu.be>

From the Curiosity and Discovery paths

- **Diane Wakim** (Ambassador - Discovery) shared her experience in adapting the curiosity activities into the discovery activities and through that, she pointed out the differences and similarities between these two paths. The curiosity activities required more guidance compared to the discovery path, since the target group of the Discovery Path are aged 18 to 25, they are mostly university students who already have a vision of things and “they want to make”. The workshops can thus be more flexible to adapt to their time and ideas. The target group for the curiosity path is mostly under 18, so the presented activities are guided since they still haven’t chosen their field yet. The two groups are instead similar in their curiosity and their initial fear of technology. Diane emphasised the importance of motivating people to do whatever they want in the lab and showing them that they’re capable of doing that.
- **Nuria Robles** (FabLab Leon - Curiosity) sees that at the curiosity stage, young girls want to look up to someone from the same age range that has the same interest as them. She explained the importance of teaching teachers how to teach technology to children, through “train the trainers” sessions.
- **Shannon Sykes** (Onl’fait - Discovery) concluded that there are two different ways to set off the spark for more knowledge and to not lose the younger generation along the way from curiosity to the discovery paths. The first is access to knowledge, ensuring access to the activities that they already have done; e.g. the shemakes toolkit that contains everything from materials to the process step by step to make it easy for them to do it. The second is access to space, welcoming participants in the labs to show them they can create whatever they want.
- **Valentine Fruchart** (Green Fabric, Brussels - Discovery) explained how the workshop at the Green Fabric lab was an opportunity for participants to learn how to innovate in the textile field, despite their zero knowledge of coding.
- **Alexandra Baltazar** (Viva Lab, Porto - Curiosity) considers maintaining the spark in the teachers to be more important since teachers are the ones that are responsible for motivating the students to use technologies.

Figure 75. Curiosity and Discovery paths Gurus and Ambassadors.

From the Lab to Lab activities

Cecilia Raspanti (Guru/ Waag) reflected on the model for wool research, capturing the vibe and synergies in between the labs and discovering an emerging ecosystem. Her Lab-to-Lab experimentation is based on two models: 1) *Journey model in 11 steps*: 9 came from the TCBL Bioshades event; however, she and Marion tried to adapt the model based on the feedback and the different contexts. The other 2 steps were added due to the knowledge exchange, research, and significantly higher number of participants; and 2) Place design and make: “that gave birth to 3 types of projects and events.” “Space for the space makers that [...] want to understand their local issue and how they can empower a certain group locally.” Based on the shemakes experience and illustrating the previous wool research, these two models could be applied to other fibres, in bio-based materials – thus discovering new research ecosystems.

Sanne Visser (Ambassador) explained that through her experience with different craft people who are linked with others from different countries, there are similarities between them that go to the multidisciplinary and to the multigenerational where’s been taught by women to women. “There’s a lot of knowledge within from women passed to women” The wool topic has been revived especially during the current climate crisis and with it gender inequality, especially that women have a lot of knowledge in making the materials. Therefore, it’s crucial to pass that traditional knowledge to the next generation and know how to do it.

Petra Garajova (Ambassador) said she couldn’t achieve much when she started her research at the university since it was difficult to get proper support there (limitations to materials research and a lack of open-source education). With her background in architecture, she was able to continue her research after joining the Fabricademy,

learning new things about the wool industry and achieving impressive results in three months with the support of her Guru Anastasia and her FabLab. She **encouraged** local participants to try different machines and materials and learn how to use local waste; some in fact worked on using laser cutting to build spinning machines.

Figure 76. Petra during the event.

From the Innovation Path and Business Engagement

- **Victor Senave** (makesense - Business Engagement) considers that to start an entrepreneurship, it is essential to gather three aspects: a) Support: Entrepreneurs have to learn different skills (knowledge about project management, communication, budgeting, etc.) by mentors or different people to have the ability to face their challenges in their projects; b) Amplify: Entrepreneurs talk about their projects, their ideas as a way to meet people and to know if people had already have tried this before; and c) Network: Entrepreneurs have to gather the right people around them as potential investors or partners. Victor, as a part of the makesense lab, explained the opportunities that the lab provides with a platform to support the entrepreneurs, to talk about their project and to link them with a network of people. It is important for young women entrepreneurs leading a successful project to hear other entrepreneurs talk about their paths, how they created something different, and how they managed to get to where they are now.
- **Beatriz Sandini** (Waag - Innovation Path) explained that although she studied business, she decided to escape the traditional fashion world after discovering Fabricademy, which opened up a different path on how innovation can take

place other than within the existing, commercialised business system. She started making biomaterials and digitally fabricated bags.

- **Alexandra Florea** (Ambassador – Business) told how, as a Romanian herself, she always wanted to do something for her local community, so she launched her own brand that uses wool leftovers. Although she works as a sustainability expert, she feels that her chemical engineering background has helped her with her brand. She shared that her journey is an exploration and research about Romanian wool and heritage. Alexandra left a message to encourage entrepreneurs to start and cross the barriers of having a business. That can only be possible by progressing step by step.
- **Carolina Tulgara** (ZIPHOUSE – Business & Innovation) shared the success story of her Ziphouse team to organise their biggest event at the end of September with 600 guest participants for a fashion show, even the President of Moldova attended. She succeeded in giving her community of young girls a voice to share their projects. She is inspired by the empowerment of the women lab leaders in Ukraine that still, through a difficult situation, keep collaborating and looking for a new normal.

Figure 77. The innovation path and business engagement conversation.

4.7. Conclusions and next steps

The Ambassadors proved to be a powerful mechanism of change for shemakes. In a bottom-up approach, they are capable of being a real inspiration to their peers, understanding that they could also inspire their local and global environment. In their work, they brought many reflections from curiosity and intuition.

The different tools developed for the Ambassadors aimed to leverage this process, providing the Ambassadors a guide to explore the shemakes ecosystem and helping the best practices of the Ambassador's journey to emerge. In this chapter, WP4 presented the practices and experiences, showing a comprehensive range of

activities and actions to bring diversity to the ecosystem, addressing not only gender but also a range of challenges in cultures, languages, and age groups. Their voices were heard through different windows of visibility, providing a space of confidence as the seeds of possible new activities and new ventures in the future.

The second round of Ambassadors included more male figures to hear voices from both sides. The inclusion of Martin and Adrian was beneficial for the exchange of opinions and to include interests in expanding the shemakes ecosystem. Compared to the first round, the second round of Ambassadors lacked the possibility to carry out activities with the Labs, leaving a feeling of a missing component in their mission. This includes the lack of one-to-one exchanges, the experience of travelling to another lab, and the on-site experience, which were all important experiences for the first round of Ambassadors. In contrast, second round Ambassadors who were able to participate in the final shemakes conference in Amsterdam had the opportunity to mix with their colleagues face-to-face, enabling a more natural exchange with the community. It is expected that in the future they will be offered more opportunities to contribute to the growth and sustainability of the shemakes community and research agenda through new connections and new projects.

5. Visibility

Task 4.1 “Visibility” aimed to promote the shemakes role models as a system. As the task was carried out in tight collaboration with WP6 Communication and Dissemination, much of the work done is reported in Deliverable 6.3. Here we mention specific aspects related to two of the role models in WP4, Advisors and Ambassadors

Advisors

In D4.2 (Reputation interim report, 31 December 2021) we introduced the program of shemakes voices, the live interview series in which project partners interview Advisors starting from a set of questions aiming to address relevant themes (routes to job, gender challenges, vision for future). At the time of that report, we had carried out four of the planned nine interviews. Due to the change in the makeup of the Advisory Board, eight interviews were finally published, of which two were previously recorded and the rest held on Facebook Live and YouTube). All interviews were promoted through custom graphics and are transcribed as blog posts to capture “long tail” search traffic. The interview with the new Advisor, Bill Macbeth, was instead conducted by email and published textually on the blog, due to digital fatigue following the initial hype created by the first set of interviews.

Ambassadors

Ambassadors provide visibility

The Ambassadors have a dissemination role that includes talking about shemakes to others and representing shemakes values and content both online and off. In order to assist them, a communication kit was provided to assist them in communicating their role as Ambassadors, including customised graphics to use on their individual social media accounts. They were encouraged to publish the images and / or a blog post - if they had a website - about their role. In addition, Ambassadors had access to the communication kit and guidelines provided to Transfer Labs, which are further detailed in D 6.3, Annex 1.

Ambassadors receive visibility

Conversely, the Ambassador profiles were uploaded to the shemakes website in the “network” section in two phases - the first 12 Ambassadors in December 2021 and the additional 18 of the second round in early October 2022. Profiles provide visibility to the Ambassadors, including where provided links to their website or social media.

Three Ambassadors were selected to tell their stories in greater detail on the blog, following a common set of questions. The stories by 1) [Tasnim](#), 2) [Marilena](#) and 3) [Petra](#) can be found on the respective blogs.

News generated by Ambassadors was shared on social media to further amplify their achievements; we shared the news on Facebook and [Instagram](#) that Petra received an important award, the "Young Scientist Award" from Lenzing in the category of the most innovative use of bio-based fibers for work based on her final project in Fabricademy. In this way, Petra's activities perfectly encapsulate the inspirational role of a shemakes Ambassador.

6. Conclusion and outlook

This deliverable presents the role of the individual contributions of 48 people between 9 Advisors, 9 Gurus and 30 Ambassadors, presenting an overview of the activities and the tools and methodologies to meet their objectives. Finally, this deliverable summarises the experiences, feedback, and reflections on the role and collective contribution to the ecosystem of women in innovation. This deliverable presents a development from M12 to M24 and presents extensively but carefully the messages and narratives of the three role model groups reflecting the positive impact and changing of perspectives in a short period. Reputation management, in this case, is interpreted as the conjunction of the narratives of the role models of the project, thus renamed as **WP4 Role models and innovation narratives** telling their own paths in building and engaging a community of innovation.

This deliverable tells the stories behind these women who, through shemakes, are illustrated to be great drivers of change and innovation. Thus, it encompasses the reflections on the leadership role in an individual and collective approach through the activities and interaction in the shemakes ecosystem.

The stories of **the advisors** tell of the role of woman innovators amplifying their voices and giving an insight into their path to achieve and perceive innovation in the T&C sector, not only in the feedback sessions but also in providing a closer look at the reality of the situation. Some of the advisors were able to participate more closely with the transfer labs. Thus, they gave valuable input and closely verified the integration processes into the proposed innovation ecosystem.

The **Gurus** had a vital role in the organisational development of the second phase. They were the driving forces of the project, accompanying the Labs from the idea to the implementation of activities. In addition, they jointly led the documentation and built strong partnerships.

The **Ambassadors** created through their role a network of innovators of excellence and represented themselves with a seed of knowledge and interchange capital, giving them a pool of possible future opportunities. In addition, they gave visibility through their experiences in the Transfer Labs and the project by participating in knowledge transfer.

The following section describes the insights from the findings on the particularities that the figures expressed in their innovation narratives and thus contributed to characterise the nature of this WP4:

6.1. Findings

The Human Factor

The involvement of individuals in different spheres and aspects such as psychological, cultural, behavioural and other human attributes influence decision-making, communication and the interpretation of information by individuals or groups. Here we represent this individuality and the interaction and input of different perceptions within the relationships of the shemakes ecosystem.

- **Sense of belonging:** this refers to feeling connected in a community that is receptive to their actions and considers the actions of others
- **Sense of agency:** through collaboration: this point speaks to the feeling that by being an agent of this ecosystem, the community establishes a safe ecosystem of interaction and trust.
- **Sense of growth:** describing the essence of evolution because of a positive change through experiences and memories and challenging members to start a new iteration. *We cannot necessarily change the industry, but the role of women can grow.*
- **Sense of urgency:** stressing the need for radical change concerning awareness and responsibility for more sustainable business and raising awareness of the need to engage with alternatives that streamline the issue with different collaborations.
- A profound transformation of the industry towards sustainability.
- **Sense of governance:** giving voice and amplifying their stories a space for debate. And taking a place to consider in the ecosystem.
- **Sense of access:** not just an open space but an open network with an open mindset that offers technological, inspirational, and collaborative opportunities.
- **Reminiscence:** memories as a tool for creating strong links and engagement with the community. It is also a tool for commitment to reputation. It reflects the idea of a long-term impact in which the young generation would be the future leaders of innovation. *Her experience of teaching in a different environment like the museum made her experience unforgettable. "Sometimes we don't value moments until they become memories."* Lucia, ambassador curiosity path.

Collaboration

it is a fundamental approach that shapes the way shemakes figures act and innovate and how they take on roles individually and collectively in the sharing community, as well as how they engage with the community to explore opportunities for interaction, some of the characteristics and qualities of collaboration are as follows.

- **Collaboration across generations:** It demonstrated the iterative work on legacy and good practices from phase to phase. In which all can support and take care of the process from generation to generation. The link between these two phases to work were the gurus. The Guru was able to learn and experience the workshops and the process of conceiving them in phase first to help them and advise the Transfer Labs to share their shemakes journey. Furthermore, this also includes the Ambassadors by guiding them in their role at the Transfer Lab. They have analysed and absorbed a lot of the methodology from the first phase and have done their best to pass it on similarly to Transfer Labs.
- **Peer to peer:** This process was most evident in the ambassadors' bottom-up inspiration. Here they empowered peers and showed a space where it can be done in small steps towards big challenges. *If you can do it, I can do it and if I can do it, we can do it!*
- **Disruptive innovation through collaboration:** shemakes develops comprehensive methods of collaboration and confrontation with realities to come back and share them in the group: *Methods and tools - collaborations - confrontation with realities - disruption transversal ways and come back to the ecosystem with strong collaborations.* This confrontation allows to have an agile reaction to the advice and the contact of a support network.
- **Collaboration in uncertainty:** The contribution to change was high during the pandemic and helped move from technological design to inclusive human-centred design driven by multidisciplinary teams. More broadly, opportunities for women are inserted into new and unexplored terrain, for example, connecting intersectionality with disability in fashion design. Uncertainty created rapid access and reaction to alternative new formats, e.g. online. In addition, these actions fostered collaboration through solidarity with the lab and positively contributed to the community in emergencies.
- **Strong relationships:** With gurus to lab leaders passing knowledge internally, helping to strategise to establish or create an audience need to the lab, Guru's transfer to lab leaders and Ambassadors support operational work such as: conception of the activities, Inventory, Relationships and connections within the ecosystem, Advice and awareness for good use of budget expenditures, drive lines of research, e.g., wool research. Create strong accountability between the

lab and the three figures: very responsive, independent and "very well organised". This example of success also creates different opportunities for collaboration by demonstrating how to develop reputational backing.

Welcoming Differences

Here we explore the different approaches to the gender gap and how they can be welcomed.

- **Embracing diversity:** We show the nuances of working together by creating a new culture through collaboration.
- **Multiplicity/ cultural pluralism:** Welcoming new ideas and respecting opinions by embracing cultures and coexisting in an enabling environment. Breaking with gender and distance via.
- **Inclusion of male opinion** As a positive part of the changes, male involvement provides opportunities to discover gaps that are not visible eg: in the textile industry. It was also a space to create their own reflections on their role. The male participation provided spaces to give women a sense of confidence to see that there are men who value and trust that they are aware of and care about bridging the gender gap.
- **Activism:** Exalting the qualities of others. Looking for ways to advocate a collective call for action.
- **Empowerment Out of the box:** Fight to find a space, challenge yourself to break out of the traditional system.
- **Embrace your strengths:** Uniqueness and positive contribution to the shemakes is a part e.g. sensitivity.
- **Develop the unconventional** Career paths discovered during the project - how people end up where they are, often following unusual trajectories and with a rich baggage of experience.

Lab as enabling environment

This section gives a brief overview of the lab providing the synergies inside and outside the lab¹⁸. It describes this confrontation with a new culture of entrepreneurship and reality and how this space is a catalyst where magic becomes reality, i.e. where opportunities can become tangible. These are some of the attributes that have emerged in relation to this environment:

¹⁸ A further and in detail explanation is provided in the D3.4 Innovation services Final Report

- **In-situ actions confrontation to the realities:** aware of the environment. This concept shows the need to have *a real vision of landscape* e.g the textile manufacturing. where it can really compete with the new collaborative ecosystems and understand that these systems can be as successful as the traditional ones. In contrast, this concept talks about the contact of placing people in different contexts facing the challenges of adapting to laboratory contexts with local resources and conditions.
- **Fast adaptation:** Lab as a place of fast response and adaptation to the context Thus, the Ambassadors describe the most significant learning experience as how to respond and adapt quickly to the public and to find quick solutions to overcome difficulties and problems.
- **Creating opportunities of transformation:** Identify opportunities and potential for transformation in the laboratories or nearby ecosystems. Here the Advisors emphasise understanding and appreciating the scope and limits that individual and collective women can interact and offer. The Ambassadors also express that the important thing here is to create the opportunity. *“You will be aware of the new opportunities that you will be having and a new one that you will be creating.”*
- **A place where dreams come true:** this space supports from the speculation to the entrepreneurship whether it is a change of perspective (what if), a launch of a project or a new activity. It is based on building the path to take the first steps. The lab becomes a reference for each target audience and supports women in getting out of their comfort zones to realise their dreams. It is a place to find peers *it did not always feel easy to understand the context of everyone, but it was “a good experience” to connect on a human level to other actors defending the same dream!*

Caring shemakes ecosystem

A concern to understand contributing to and ultimately caring for the innovation ecosystem as a form of engagement and belonging here are some characteristics of this feeling:

- **Listen to others:** in this way, understand, have unique empathy and welcome colleagues towards goals and overcoming fears to talk.
- **Sense of appreciation:** for the opportunities and seed capital provided by shemakes as a boost and future opportunities offered by the ecosystem. Sense of gratitude for the role and experience accumulated in the collective.

- **Confidence and trust:** sharing experiences and ideas and contributing with a passion to their work, feeling a safe space to overcome fear and grow in confidence.

Methodologies

Implementing methods and tools for innovation through systematic dynamism but simultaneously in the language and modus operandi of the innovation ecosystem was fundamental. From a WP4 perspective, we introduced some points that highlighted shemakes' role models.

- **Innovation analysis:** Reflects the importance of a first understanding of the agile methods and the diversity of how labs approach innovation. We can see the clustering of methods, tools, and frameworks that each Guru and Transfer Labs Leader is implementing daily and sharing these tools in the community.
- **Introducing the values at the core of innovation:** Agile methods describe how to collaborate in the innovation ecosystem. It illustrates that perhaps industry structures cannot be changed but that the values brought by shemakes can become more powerful when changing dynamics across each of their actors and spaces. Some of the complementary values to those already stated in the shemakes vision have been named as part of the methodology:
 - **Courage:** The need for courage and passion for standing up for one's mentality, for reflecting on gender issues and for developing independence of thought and work. It is an individual value and is part of the methodology that refers to personal initiative. It also requires risk-taking, networking, responsibility for people, and the ecosystem's relationship.
 - **Optimism and kindness:** Positive change is first based on optimistic inspiration towards other people, women and men. "Optimism is activism", as it helps reach more people willing to contribute to more positive change.
- **Open Toolkit and sketchbooks:** The online and offline tools for inspiration, guidance and self-reflection contained in the open toolkit and the sketchbooks in printed or online versions started building routines that enable a better understanding and follow the process from the beginning of the role as Ambassadors.
- **Learning-, by-doing -teaching:** To adapt and learn by doing, it is important to interact with the environment and put hands on action. After different interactions as a participant and as a collaborator, it is possible to teach and transfer this knowledge to your peers, finally this method can propose you to

be a leader of your own activities and to develop your own variations and interests.

- **Mentoring towards sponsorship:** The role of mentoring is an essential part of the methodology to empower women to undertake an initiative or new business. To connect the other roles with the team or individuals with related skills and with a network of support persons who can mentor and advise. Mentoring is part of the added value, with a high content of knowledge and skills transfer.
- **Visibility windows:** Constant contact and sharing of stories in different groups, the visibility of peer-to-peer work, as part of their inspirational role, with the network and finally, with the media, understanding in this visibility of a genuinely inspirational role for their community. Such windows can be extended externally through social media, e.g. Instagram highlighting what women can do concerning the significant gender/circularity/climate challenges. It means not only having a ripple effect but tackling the problems and interests that are relevant in the community.

6.2. Barriers and improvement opportunities

Barriers

- **Resistance to the introduction of the gender theme:** There was some confusion in introducing the gender theme in specific guidelines at the beginning of the project. Some found it challenging to raise the gender theme in the activities. Understanding gender barriers was the first step.
- **The bubble within the laboratories:** As there are already places where women are well integrated and share the same values, it is difficult to perceive the differences, while in other contexts, such as industry, the differences are more evident, which leads to the conclusion: "if we do not share experiences and give opportunities to new generations, there will never be a change and growth!"
- **Gender issues in finance:** Women, as the number of opportunities and investors, is also male-oriented.
- **Gender issues in technology:** There is still a perception that men dominate technical and engineering fields. This results in the prejudice that technology is "a difficult subject" to integrate into their products.
- **Cultural barriers** Cultural differences sometimes made support difficult. To offer the proper support, it is essential to be aware of the natural barriers to

entrepreneurship in countries other than the local one, as well as the political situation e.g. the war in Ukraine made planning difficult.

Improvement opportunities

- **Time-based efforts with youth Ambassadors:** Youth Ambassadors need more support, as they are not autonomous and need guidance from you is crucial to consider this when designing project-type efforts.
- **Review of the budget plan:** Including some budget for attending meetings and understanding best practices for spending the budget.
- **Scheduling:** Synchronise the attendance schedules of different target groups e.g. children could not attend all meetings in the morning.
- **Evaluation:** As the activities were planned and it was the first time they were done; some needed more time to prepare the evaluation of the activities.

6.3. Further steps

- **Methodologies:** provide an institutional framework for sustainability.
- **Application and further development of tangible and intangible heritage tools:** Values, open toolbox within reputation management, the shemakes set of values took up significant space in developing an intangible heritage. The Open Toolkit is a tangible legacy for future generations to build within the labs' network and different labs that expressed an interest in joining and applying the dissemination of this content.
- **Shemakes Club:** shemakes is a growing network, merging with the TCBL lab network, but forming a "Shemakes Club" within TCBL to give continuity to the project's actions, meeting online and in person at regular intervals.
- **Follow-up networks:** Fostering the development of interdisciplinary networks and follow-up of networks born through shemakes, e.g. the French-speaking network of maker labs in France, the network between Portugal and Spain of child entrepreneurs. These networks started in the exchange between gurus and transfer lab leaders, evidence of further developing partnerships hosting other types of initiatives.
- **Governance:** In the framework of TCBL and Fabricademy as an invitation to join both ecosystems of education and development of entrepreneurial skills.
- **Ambassadors:** An opportunity was opened for ambassadors; to further build the ecosystem through existing connections and initiatives they have already created and options provided for existing ecosystems to continue to develop their roles in sharing and disseminating the innovation narratives shemakes.

- **Autonomous Ecosystem:** Through the experience of the interaction between transfer labs, gurus and Ambassadors, becoming more self-reliant and engaged in the community. This self-driven mindset evidence the wish to continue the collaboration. Like the wool projects and collaborations illustrated well why and how labs could synchronise their research effort on one topic and contribute within a peer learning mindset to face societal challenges.

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